

UNDERGRADUATE SPECIAL PROJECT/CAPSTONE

Bachelor of Education Studies (BES)

**UNIVERSITY OF THE PHILIPPINES
OPEN UNIVERSITY**

BACHELOR OF EDUCATION STUDIES

JOSE ALBERTO RAFAEL M. MEDINA

**FINANCIAL LITERACY FOR THE UNIVERSITY OF THE PHILIPPINES INDUSTRIAL
ENGINEERING STUDENTS ORGANIZATION MEMBERS**

Special/Capstone Project Adviser:

**LEYNARD L. GRIPAL
Faculty of Education**

4 August 2025

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Acceptance Page

This special/capstone project prepared by **JOSE ALBERTO RAFAEL M. MEDINA** with the title: “**FINANCIAL LITERACY FOR THE UNIVERSITY OF THE PHILIPPINES INDUSTRIAL ENGINEERING STUDENTS ORGANIZATION MEMBERS**” is hereby accepted by the Faculty of Education, U.P. Open University, in partial fulfillment of the requirements for the degree of Bachelor of Education Studies.

Leynard L. Gripal, LPT
FIC/Adviser

(Date)

Celeste Laurel Tayzon, PhD
Program Chair

(Date)

Charisse T. Reyes, PhD

Dean
Faculty of Education

Day Month Year
(Date)

Biographical Sketch

Jose Alberto Rafael M. Medina was born to Oliver R. Medina and Celia M. Medina on August 15, 1996, in Quezon City. He is the youngest of 2 children and He is currently residing in Taguig, Philippines.

He completed primary and secondary school at Statefields School Inc. in 2013. Previously enrolled in BS Industrial Engineering at the University of the Philippines Los Baños, he shifted to Bachelor of Education Studies at the University of the Philippines Open University due to different circumstances.

Acknowledgement

I dedicate this project to my family—my mom, dad, sister, and aunts—who never gave up on me and continued to support me throughout the many twists and turns of my academic life. I also dedicate it to Jule, who inspires me to be better every day.

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Abstract

This study uses the ADDIE framework to explore the design, implementation, and evaluation of a financial literacy workshop for the University of the Philippines Los Baños Industrial Engineering Students Organization (UPLB IESO). Grounded in constructivist, experiential, and adult learning theories, the workshop incorporated interactive learning strategies, including game-based learning with financial literacy games such as CASHFLOW, STAX, and SHADY SAM.

Key findings from the implementation highlighted the importance of practical application, scaffolding, and differentiated instruction in addressing students' diverse financial knowledge. Challenges included time constraints, technical barriers due to online delivery, and engagement difficulties in a virtual setting.

Self-evaluation revealed strengths in instructional design, particularly in constructive alignment, multimedia principles, and assessment selection. However, the study also underscored the presenter's limitations in public speaking and the need for greater emphasis on instructional design rather than solely teaching. The project further emphasized the gaps in financial literacy education in the Philippines and the need for accessible learning resources.

Ultimately, this capstone project demonstrates the critical role of effective instructional design in financial literacy education and provides recommendations for future iterations, including enhanced engagement strategies, improved material accessibility, and better integration of game-based learning.

Keywords: Financial Literacy, Instructional Design, Game-Based Learning, ADDIE Framework, Online Learning, Constructivist Theory, Experiential Learning

I. INTRODUCTION

Rationale

Financial literacy is crucial in our daily lives, spanning everything from purchasing household necessities to effectively managing funds for day-to-day expenses, and involving basic fiscal concepts such as saving, budgeting, debt management, and investing (Garg & Singh, 2018). It enables individuals to manage their finances wisely, achieve financial goals, and make prudent decisions across various aspects of personal financing. This knowledge is particularly valuable for organizations like the Industrial Engineering Students Organization (IESO). Grounded in core values of efficiency, professionalism, and excellence, IESO aims to cultivate competent, skilled, and versatile members through diverse activities such as workshops, seminars, and participating in national organizations such as the Philippine Institute for Industrial Engineering (PIIE).

Executive Summary

Based on the 2019 Financial Inclusion Survey conducted by the Bangko Sentral ng Pilipinas (BSP), it was found that only 55% of adults in the Philippines have a clear understanding of inflation. (BSP, 2019). This issue arises because financial literacy isn't included in the basic education curriculum in the country. Instead, people often learn about finances informally rather than through organized educational channels, which could offer a more thorough understanding starting from childhood or before they begin working. After conducting a brief survey among the organization's current members and alumni, it was observed that a significant portion of students lack foundational financial

literacy, leaving them to fend for themselves in terms of managing their financial affairs without proper guidance. This further emphasizes the importance of exploring how teaching financial literacy in schools could help Filipinos better understand financial concepts and make smarter budgetary decisions.

Understanding and promoting financial literacy among students and young graduates is crucial for equipping them with the skills needed to make informed financial decisions early in their careers. This proposal addresses the significant gap in formal financial education by exploring effective ways to enhance financial literacy, ensuring individuals are prepared to achieve financial stability and success.

Objectives of the study

Learning Objectives

At the end of the workshop, the participants should be able to:

1. Demonstrate a comprehensive understanding of financial concepts, including savings, investments, governmental deductions, and loan options.
2. Create and manage their own balance sheets, budget effectively, and track expenses.
3. Identify and evaluate various investment options and understand the principles of passive income to grow their savings.
4. Utilize modern financial tools and platforms for efficient money management.
5. Engage with accessible and relevant financial content tailored to their background and language proficiency.

Personal Objectives

At the end of the workshop, I should be able to

1. Effectively apply the key lessons learned from the BES curriculum in the context of teaching and practice.
2. Develop and implement assessments that accurately measure student learning and provide valuable feedback without causing unnecessary stress.

II. REVIEW OF RELATED LITERATURE

Theoretical Framework

Financial literacy is a crucial life skill that enables individuals to make informed financial decisions, yet many struggle with fundamental concepts such as budgeting, saving, and investing. The 2019 Financial Inclusion Survey conducted by the Bangko Sentral ng Pilipinas (BSP) highlights the alarming state of financial literacy in the Philippines, revealing that a significant portion of the population lacks basic financial knowledge. This gap underscores the necessity of integrating financial education into formal and informal learning environments to empower individuals with essential money management skills.

Garg and Singh (2018) emphasize the importance of financial literacy among youth, arguing that early exposure to financial concepts enhances financial decision-making skills later in life. Their study found that young individuals who engage with financial education programs demonstrate improved savings habits and a better understanding of credit management.

Conceptual Framework

Several key financial concepts form the foundation of financial literacy, including assets, liabilities, cash flow, and taxation. According to Goff (2023), understanding the relationship between assets, liabilities, and equity is essential for managing personal and business finances. Assets contribute to an individual's or organization's wealth, while liabilities represent financial obligations. Equity, the residual interest in assets after deducting liabilities, serves as a measure of financial health.

In addition, Hayes (n.d.) defines cash flow as the movement of money in and out of an entity, highlighting its critical role in assessing financial stability. Proper cash flow management allows individuals to maintain liquidity and avoid debt accumulation, making it a fundamental topic in financial literacy education.

Taxation also plays a significant role in financial literacy. The concept of value-added tax (VAT), as explained by The Investopedia Team (n.d.), is a consumption tax levied at each stage of production and distribution. Meanwhile, mandatory contributions to government social security programs, such as Pag-IBIG and SSS, are essential financial obligations for employees in the Philippines (Nikki, 2024a; 2024b). Understanding these deductions helps individuals plan their finances more effectively.

Gamification in Financial Literacy Education

The use of game-based learning in financial literacy education has gained traction due to its effectiveness in engaging learners and simplifying complex financial concepts. Kapp (n.d.) explores the role of game elements in learning, emphasizing how mechanics such as abstraction, rules, and time constraints can enhance

comprehension and retention. Studies have shown that interactive and experiential learning methods, such as financial literacy games, can significantly improve students' ability to apply financial knowledge in real-world scenarios.

By integrating financial literacy concepts with gamified learning experiences, educators can create engaging and effective workshops. This approach aligns with Edgar Dale's Cone of Experience, which suggests that learners retain more knowledge when they actively engage in practical activities rather than passive learning.

The reviewed literature underscores the critical need for financial literacy education, particularly among young individuals, and highlights the effectiveness of gamified learning strategies in teaching financial concepts. The integration of real-world financial topics—such as assets, liabilities, cash flow, taxation, and government contributions—into interactive learning experiences can significantly enhance students' financial competencies. These insights inform the design of financial literacy programs that are both engaging and educational, addressing the gaps identified in financial inclusion surveys and prior research.

III. METHODOLOGY

Research Design

By utilizing the ADDIE method (Analyze, Design, Develop, Implement, and Evaluate), my objective is to create a financial literacy workshop for the organization, focused on guiding students with essential knowledge before they enter the workforce. Initially, I will analyze the participants to establish their current understanding as a

baseline. Subsequently, I will design the workshop content to resonate with the contemporary generation, utilizing diverse media formats that align with current trends. The development plan will involve crafting a detailed lesson plan and interactive activities to foster student engagement and assess knowledge retention. Implementation will occur with a control group comprising five current organization members, from whom feedback will be gathered for evaluation purposes.

Additionally, the workshop aims to empower participants with practical financial skills, encouraging proactive financial management and informed decision-making. By using real-world examples and interactive activities, students will gain hands-on experience applying financial concepts to their own lives. This approach not only enhances understanding but also builds confidence in managing finances effectively. Ultimately, the workshop seeks to equip students with the tools needed for lifelong financial independence and stability.

ADDIE Model

ADDIE is a famous framework for the design process which stands for Analysis, Design, Development, Implementation, and Evaluation. I chose ADDIE because it could be used to create entirely new training campaigns or to improve existing ones. As new information and research gets published every day regarding fiscal literacy, this framework could then be applied into existing models in order to improve educational efficiency making sure that the information that the students would receive would be up-to-date, relevant, and applicable to the current market environment along with their level of proficiency. Aside from that, due to the different limitations of the study such as the number of times that a pilot testing could be held, models such as Michael Allen;s

Successive Approximation Model that require multiple iterations would not be feasible for the situation.

ANALYSIS – In order to gain complete insight on what the learners would require, the first step necessary as per EDS 112 – Principles of Instructional Design would be a Needs Analysis for the target audience. A needs assessment would be necessary to identify gaps between what students currently know vs what they must know to be considered financially literate. I opted to use an intensive needs assessment in order to come up with a needs, learner, institution, and technological analysis for the workshop.

Learner Needs

1. Methodology

Data was gathered using a combination of observation, survey, interviews, and previous information that I know of regarding the university, organization, and the members for both qualitative and quantitative data to be able to apply a mixed method research that I have learned from EDS 196 – Education Research Methods. I opted to use a mixed method research in order to avoid the pitfalls and shortcomings of using only one type of data. Participants would be current members of the organization; 18 years old and above, enrolled in the university, coming from diverse socio-economic backgrounds. However, they have varying prior knowledge regarding the topic. As a pre-assessment and background check, a short survey comprising 5 current members and 5 alumni of the organization. I included 5 alumni in the survey as a control group to show what is currently happening without the intervention of a workshop. For ease of data gathering, the survey was done online through Google Forms so that information gathered would already be visually presented afterwards. The specific aim of the need's

assessment is to pinpoint the importance of financial knowledge for upcoming professionals, highlight the need for financial literacy in the country's basic curriculum, and develop actual content and assessments that will be used for the workshop.

Locale of the study

Figure 1 – UPLB IESO Logo

Institution Description:

The financial literacy program will be implemented at the University of the Philippines Los Baños Industrial Engineering Students Organization (UPLB IESO).. This organization was chosen due to its strong academic reputation and its commitment to values such as efficiency, professionalism, and continuous improvement. The organization's focus on both academic and personal development makes it an ideal setting for a financial literacy initiative.

Technical Landscape

There are two possible options of implementation for the workshop, face-to-face instruction and via online synchronous classes.

Learning Environment:

If face-to-face instruction is chosen for the workshop, there is no place better to hold it than at The UPLB Department of Industrial Engineering since IESO is the only acknowledged academic organization of the department, members are provided free usage of the department's facilities. The department offers a well-equipped learning environment. It includes a lecture hall for up to 60 students and four air-conditioned rooms—three classrooms and a computer lab. Technology in the classrooms includes LCD projectors in Rooms 100 and 101, 60" HD flat screen TVs in Rooms 103 and 104, and a 42" HD flat screen TV in Room 102. The computer lab, accommodating over 20 students, is equipped with relevant software. Lastly, the UPLB Wifi reaches into the department which would provide students with reliable fast internet connection. These facilities will be able to support the delivery of the financial literacy program effectively and create an engaging learning experience.

Suppose online instruction is chosen on the other hand, given that they are college students who have adapted to online learning during the pandemic. In that case, it is expected that they will have access to electronic devices with internet connectivity.

DESIGN – The next step in the ADDIE framework is the design phase where learning objectives, content structure, and instructional technologies that are going to be used are defined. Here lessons from EDS 112 – Principles of Instructional Design and EDUC 103 – Theories of Learning come into play as I start to design the workshop.

Following Bigg's constructive alignment, my goal is for students to be able to learn about financial literacy.

CONTENT STRUCTURE

To achieve the said objectives, a rough outline was created along with Kyla Salvacion, the Vice President for Properties and Holdings of UPLB IESO after we talked about the lack and need of a financial literacy workshop for the organization.

Financial Literacy

- I. Overview
 - Budgeting, taxes, loans, savings, investments
 - Savings and budgeting
 - Importance of financial literacy and applications
 - Banks, electronic wallets, cash
 - Dividing income – expense, support, emergency, retirement
- II. Investments
 - Stocks, forex, crypto – dividends and capital appreciation, investor vs trader
 - Money cost averaging
 - Bonds, treasuries, insurance
- III. Contributions, Loans, and taxes
 - SSS and pagibig – different types of loans and required contributions
 - Types of taxes
 - Income tax
 - Train law

Figure 2 Lesson Plan V1 - Financial Literacy

The financial literacy workshop will be divided into three segments or sessions starting with foundational sessions covering basic financial concepts like budgeting, savings, and the importance of financial literacy to ensure a solid understanding before moving on to more complex topics. This method ensured that everyone could build a solid foundation before tackling advanced material such as investment education,

offering insights on examples such as stocks, bonds, and cryptocurrencies to highlight their potential for passive income. Technology integration will be featured through live demonstrations of digital tools such as online banking and e-wallets. Finally, government mandated contributions, taxes, and loan options would be introduced in preparation for once they start working and earning salaries. Bilingual and inclusive instruction will be provided using diverse methods to cater to various learning preferences and ensure clarity.

Using the information gained from EDUC 103 – Theories of learning and EDS 131 – Foundations of Adult Education, the workshop was developed using educational theories that correspond respectively to the approaches and strategies used knowing that theories selected would affect instruction method and focus:

Theories of Teaching and Learning:

Constructivist Theory (Piaget, Vygotsky): Emphasizes that learners build on prior knowledge and experiences. The bottom-up approach aligns with this theory by starting with foundational concepts and advancing to complex topics, allowing learners to construct knowledge progressively. It focuses on building a strong foundation and interactive learning, which helps apply knowledge in practical ways by assimilating or accommodating new information into an existing schema. Constructivism also advocates active student-centered learning where instructors guide students into creating their own ideas regarding the topic.

Experiential Learning (Kolb): Highlights the importance of learning through experience. Interactive activities and practical exercises are grounded in this theory,

facilitating learning by doing and reinforcing theoretical understanding through real-life application.

Adult Learning Theory (Knowles): Focuses on the unique needs and motivations of adult learners. The program incorporates practical, relevant content and acknowledges participants' prior experiences, aligning with the principles of self-directed learning and applicability to real-life scenarios.

Approaches and Strategies:

Bottom-Up Approach: Begin with basic concepts and progressively build to more complex topics to ensure a comprehensive understanding for all participants. Financial literacy requires a basic understanding of fiscal terms and processes that would be necessary before proceeding to complex topics such as investments and loans.

Interactive Learning: Utilize hands-on activities, discussions, and practical exercises to engage students and facilitate active learning. I believe that experience is the best teacher, learning would be much deeper if internal cognitive processes are complemented by a concrete experience.

Case-Based Learning: Integrate real-life examples and case studies to illustrate financial principles and investment strategies, making content relevant and relatable in different situations that they would experience as adult working members of the society. I also believe that smart people learn from their mistakes but smarter people learn from other people's mistakes. Case studies would provide situations that they could follow or avoid. It would also familiarize them with cases that they would definitely experience as adults.

These theories were chosen instead of behaviorist theories because the latter works best for younger learners as it focuses on instrumental conditioning and consequence which would also require time and familiarization between student and instructor. Cognitive theories were also not chosen due to there being no memorization required. Although applications of cognitive load theory and dual-coding theory would be brushed up on during the development of the multimedia material. The chosen theories would also affect assessments developed for the workshop and would be discussed on the next step of the ADDIE model.

The methods chosen for the financial literacy workshop are designed to maximize learning and relevance. A bottom-up approach is used to build understanding incrementally, starting with fundamental concepts and progressing to more complex topics, ensuring that all participants develop a comprehensive grasp of the material. Interactive learning methods are integrated to enhance engagement and retention by allowing students to apply their knowledge in practical scenarios. Additionally, case-based learning is employed to provide practical insights and real-world context, helping students connect theoretical concepts with actual financial practices.

After considering the model, approaches, strategies, and theories that would be used for the workshop, a detailed lesson plan was then created

DEVELOP – In this step of the ADDIE framework, training materials, multimedia content, assessments, and learning activities would be decided. Knowledge gained from EDS 151 – Instructional Media Resources, EDS 153 – Design of Educational

Multimedia, and EDS 113 – Principles and Methods of Assessment materials were especially helpful in this phase.

Training Materials

Since there is already a completed learning outline from the previous step, the next thing to do would be to create training materials for the workshop. The first thing I decided to do is the powerpoint presentation that utilized a lot of different concepts from different courses. There are a variety of supplementary materials to choose from that would be useful for a workshop aside from the traditional visual aid such as the powerpoint. However, keeping in mind the possibility of implementing the course wherein different instructor's would take over for the presentation, it seemed best to provide the option of personalization up to them. The training materials are also meant to supplement the workshop instead of complement it. The class should be able to proceed even if there would be a power interruption or if the media files get corrupted. A powerpoint would also be the most efficient type of multimedia that I could produce as there is already a lot of material on the internet that would suffice and were created by people with more budget, time, and skill. There are a variety of videos available on Video, Youtube, Tiktok, and other platforms that instructors could include in the workshop. By using the different effects of multimedia starting with the coherence effect, the powerpoint was made with a minimalist design so as to cover the bases without too much flair that could distract the students considering the student's cognitive load. I chose to keep it simple, removing any irrelevant material and focusing only on relevant information. As long as both visual and verbal channels are provided, the multimedia effect would already be fulfilled. It was also ensured that the powerpoint was developed

with the principles of visual design such as spatial contiguity, in mind to make sure that it is not only visually and aesthetically pleasing but also fulfills the necessary effect. Lastly, personal and conversational language is used instead of jargon and formal tone so that students would be able to connect to the content easily. Examples are also not included so that the instructors could create inclusive examples that students would be able to relate to as it changes quickly depending on the current trend. Inclusion and representation would also provide instructors with opportunities to engage students like asking for real-life examples

Data Gathering Procedure

Assessments aid reflective teaching by giving educators an insight on what happens inside their student's minds. A quick snapshot of how their students process the information that was given to them and how it progresses with each new lesson. It also determines if goals of education are being met. Therefore, the assessments for the workshop were based on information from EDS 155 – Game-based learning and EDS 113 – Principles and methods of assessment where different types of assessment were introduced to align with their advantages and disadvantages. It was decided that informal assessments would be used throughout the workshop to keep the atmosphere light and enjoyable, avoid stifling formality, and minimize adding to the pressure that they already experience daily while studying at the university. Summative assessments therefore are not necessary as it provides a limited snapshot of student achievement and some students do not test well. Constructivist principles guide non-traditional assessments by definition, it engages students, making them responsible for their own learning. It strays from the typical formal assessments where information flows in one

direction, instead knowledge is formulated and constructed by the parties involved along the way using pre-existing knowledge.

To break the ice, diagnostic assessments would be applied in the form of game-based learning to encourage students via interactive and entertaining activities.

Following Kapp's understanding of Game elements, Abstraction of concepts and reality is important as it provides a number of advantages such as:

- Manage conceptual space
- Cause and effect is easily identified
- Abstracting removes extraneous factors
- Reduces time required to grasp concepts

Abstraction of complex topics by using games define clear goals, rules, time limit, reward structures, and provide immediate feedback. Players also get to "do over", allowing failure and providing the opportunity to fail without the consequence such as losing their money or being buried in debt. Failure also creates a deeper impact that affects knowledge retention. The games chosen are also short and direct to the point to reduce cognitive load and to avoid players losing themselves in the game instead of focusing on the learning opportunity as is supported by the cognitive load theory by Sweller. It also follows the constructivist concept of "advancing by doing," used in this digital age through game-based learning, in which students can learn how to analyze and solve problems for themselves through the implementation of games.

I have chosen CASHFLOW for module 1, STAX for module 2, and SHADY SAM for module 3. These games were chosen in order to gauge students' prior knowledge regarding the topic at hand. CashFlow is a board game created by Robert Kiyosaki

which includes concepts about assets, liabilities, income, and expenses. Stax brought to us by Next Gen Personal Financing introduces all different types of investing and comes with a companion sheet to boot. And lastly, Shady Sam demonstrates how loan terms work and affect borrowers who sign without understanding the fine print.

IV. RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

Results and Findings

Based on the survey, 80% of the students currently have savings while only 60% of the alumni have. The alumni are more aware of the different investing options while students only know of a few with 20% of them unaware. Only 20% of the students currently have an investment while 40% of alumni don't have any investments. Though all of the alumni are aware of the deductions in their monthly salary, most of them are not aware of the actual ranges of the deductions made by the different governmental bodies while only a handful of students know of some. The students and 40% of the alumni are also unaware of the loan options offered by the government. Students are keen on learning about financial literacy early to achieve their financial goals more effectively. Alumni have often gained this awareness later in life, highlighting a need for earlier intervention.

Gaps and Needs Identified:

- Varying Prior Knowledge: Participants have different levels of understanding regarding basic financial concepts.
- Practical Application: Need for practical exercises to apply theoretical knowledge in real-life scenarios.

- Investment Knowledge: Lack of exposure to various investment options and understanding of how to grow savings.
- Technological Proficiency: Requirement to familiarize students with modern financial tools and platforms.
- Inclusivity: Ensuring content is accessible and engaging for all students.

Instructional Problems

Content would definitely be the first and foremost problem regarding financial literacy. There is a lot of information, content, and strategy already available on the internet and the main challenge would be choosing which one would be most effective considering that the participants would be students with only their allowance or stipends as their source of income. Aside from that, the venue and schedule should also be considered since university class schedule is held from 7 am – 7 pm and if there are any, examinations of major subjects held from 7 – 9 pm. The workshop schedule therefore should not interfere with the student’s priorities and should avoid what the students lovingly refer to as “hell weeks”.

The main discussion would follow after the games and then the students will engage in practical informal formative exercises, keeping in line with the constructivist and experiential outline. These exercises are designed with the key factors in mind:

- Understand the purpose and nature of assessment
- Put in place processes to ensure academic integrity
- Focus on designing valid assessment
- Identify appropriate points of assessment
- Take into account workloads of student and staff

- Communicate the assessment requirements using plain language
- Provide timely and constructive feedback

In module 1 students would be asked to create their own balance sheets, identifying their assets and liabilities. In module 2, they will be asked to create a trial account in Etoro, a forex trading platform where they could practice with cryptocurrencies, shares, and exchange-traded funds (ETFs). Module 3 would ask them to compute hypothetical salary deductions depending on different situations. After each activity, time will be allotted for feedback as it is important to make sure that students have the correct idea in mind before ending the session. Utilizing information gained on these assessments would help an educator with improving his or her way of teaching, providing additional time and effort for difficult topics that students have pointed out. One formative assessment per module would be sufficient in order to determine student learning and instructor effectiveness as adding more may overload students and unnecessary since required information is already gathered. Creating a personalized teaching process that would cater to their students at a personal level to a certain extent, forging a bond with the student as they feel important, attended to, and valuable in a learner-centered paradigm.

Applying Edgar Dale's Cone of Experience, students would be exposed to the three modes of learning experience. Symbolic as they learn through the abstractions of verbal and visual symbols from the instructor and the multimedia material. Iconic as they learn through observations gathered in the class via real-life examples, case studies, and represented data. And lastly, Direct, purposeful experience as they learn by doing when they participate in the assessments provided in the workshop.

IMPLEMENT

The workshop was then implemented for pilot testing on August 11, 2024 at 8 PM. It is the students semester break therefore there was no choice but to implement the class using online methods applying information learned from EDS 157 – Online Teaching and Learning. I opted to use Anderson’s model of online learning which has 4 principles:

Learner-centredness – includes language and expression

Knowledge-centered – scaffolding information

Assessment-centered – formative assessments to lessen instructor workload

Community-centered – existence of social networks as they belong in one organization

The class was initially scheduled to start by 7 pm. However, due to some students experiencing technical and connection difficulties, the workshop was delayed as we waited for their zoom to update and internet connection to stabilize. The actual class time breakdown is as follows:

30 mins – icebreaker

20 mins – discussion proper

10 mins – assessment

5 mins – wrap up

We started with playing CASHFLOW as planned but was unable to finish the game even with an extended time frame. The main discussion proceeded without trouble and ample time was provided for their assessment. However, there was not enough time for the feedback as the whole session already exceeded an hour and that is without accounting for the postponement.

The whole seminar is available at Youtube through the link:

<https://youtu.be/CkXZTFqE9jg>

Figure 7 Picture with the seminar participants

V. SUMMARY, CONCLUSION, AND RECOMMENDATIONS

Summary

EVALUATE

Several significant insights emerged from the financial literacy teaching sessions:

- **Practical Application:** Hands-on activities, like creating balance sheets and budgeting, greatly enhanced student engagement and understanding. Real-world applications proved crucial for effective learning.
- **Diverse Prior Knowledge:** Students had varying levels of prior financial knowledge. Some grasped concepts quickly due to previous coursework, while others needed extra support, highlighting the need for differentiated instruction.

- **Importance of Feedback:** Immediate feedback would've cleared misconceptions immediately within the session cementing concepts and improving retention.
- **Time constraint:** The diagnostic activity was not finished due to the time required for explanation and familiarization with the interface and rules.

During the implementation of the financial literacy project, a few key adjustments were made from the original plan. Since the project was done through an online class, there were varying levels of internet access and technology issues among students. The workshop was delayed as we waited for some participants, some disconnected at random times due to unstable internet connection as I've learned later that one is even travelling onboard a jeep. These issues could have been avoided if the class was held on site. Providing the materials beforehand would also be helpful to give them time to download and view them offline.

My limitations as a presenter were also brought up as there were dry or dull moments during the workshop. It was hard to engage students through the zoom meeting as they opted to chat or react instead of actually speaking up. The workshop may benefit from inviting a professional that may be able to host a livelier class.

Another issue was the wide range of prior knowledge about finance among the students. Some were familiar with the basics, while others were new to the concepts. I addressed this by making sure to go through the basics to make sure that each student would have an equal and stable foundation.

There was not enough time to finish the icebreaker activity, which in turn took time from providing feedback to the formative assessment that was scheduled after the discussion. Having experienced this several times from different learning approaches,

there are some common solutions that have been applied by previous instructors such as extending the class, postponing the feedback to the next session which would have defeated the advantages of immediate feedback, or by cutting the activity at an earlier time which leaves the students disappointed as they are just starting to enjoy the game as they get the hang of it which was what happened with the class. For future applications, however, I have opted to change the diagnostic activity for module 1 instead. I replaced it with SPENT, where players survive the struggle of low-income living.

Figure 4 Student Feedback 1

FEEDBACK

- While I was not able to play the game, it was very helpful that these concepts were introduced/presented in a more interactive manner. This helps the audience easily understand them by having to experience it themselves.
- As an individual who's not getting any younger, I admire the discussion related to financial literacy as it would be beneficial for me to be a responsible adult. Lately, I'm into tracking my expenses and this discussion helps a lot.
- It was an interesting topic, and the activity helped clarify things. It made me realize the important aspects of financial literacy, and I had fun. Overall, the presentation was straightforward and easy to understand, and it didn't take much time, so I didn't feel bored.
- The workshop was very informative and engaging. I especially enjoyed the Cashflow game. Although we didn't get to finish it, the game still highlighted key financial concepts in a fun and interactive way. The discussion afterward was just as beneficial, particularly the insights on how to manage income and expenses effectively, as well as the clear explanation of what counts as actual assets and liabilities. These concepts are especially valuable for college students like us, who deal with a lot of financial responsibilities and challenges.
- The class was not only informative but it was also very interactive.

SUGGESTIONS

- Additional tips on how to manage finances well will help
- The presentation was great but lacked engagement, so I suggest adding more activities to encourage participant involvement before the game. I also recommend giving participants an idea of what to expect before the start of the class to ensure a smoother flow.
- One suggestion for improvement would be to allocate more time to ensure that the Cashflow game can be completed. Finishing the game would likely reinforce the lessons | learned and provide a more comprehensive understanding of financial strategies. Though this issue is understandable since many delays were encountered before and during the workshop.
- Effectiveness of the class could be improved if in person learning was implemented

Figure 5 Student Feedback 2

Conclusion

From this project, I learned that starting with basic concepts before moving to more complex ones is crucial for effective teaching. Scaffolding information gives students sufficient prior information for them to build up on the succeeding lessons as it was

explained in the Constructivist theory. I also realized that hands-on activities and real-world examples make a big difference in how well students grasp financial concepts. Applying Edgar Dale's Cone of experience, the students were able to enjoy and learn more by demonstrations and direct purposeful experiences. As an educator, it's clear that understanding and addressing students' varying levels of knowledge is key to successful instruction. This project also highlighted how important it is to integrate practical financial education into the Philippine curriculum, where such topics are often overlooked.

In the broader context, the project showed me that the lack of financial literacy in the Philippine education system needs urgent attention. Social and educational conditions like limited resources and unequal access to learning materials impact how effectively these programs can be implemented. To improve, there needs to be better support for educational programs and more accessible resources for students across different regions.

Self-Evaluation

The program successfully improved financial literacy of students involved as feedback indicated a significant improvement in understanding personal finance. I was also able to apply numerous lessons learned from different BES subjects along the way. Through the ADDIE framework, I was able to effectively Analyze through a thorough needs, context, learner, and institution analysis using mixed methods research. Though some subjects included in the course were not directly applied, due to the diverse background of viable learners, some topics could still be useful such as EDS – 133 Islamic Education and EDS 154 – Assistive Learning Technologies in dealing with

muslim and physically-challenged participants. Design and Develop went hand in hand as I set and was able to use constructive alignment to set a goal, achieve SMART (Specific, Manageable, Achievable, Relevant, and Timebound) objectives for the workshop and provide outcomes that were evaluated properly through different assessments applied. Constructivist, Experiential, and Adult Learning theories were utilized throughout the whole design in order to ensure scaffolded information would be properly applied through hands-on experiences that would be relevant to their personal and professional lives. Creation of the multimedia material also went smoothly as I applied the effects of multimedia according to Mayer's promise of multimedia learning in the powerpoint presentation which also follows the elements and principles of design. The different options for multimedia were also considered before choosing to create a powerpoint. I am specifically proud of the assessments chosen for the workshop as I was able to apply knowledge learned constructively as it also took me several hours to look for and try different games that would fit perfectly with the modules that would embody Kapp's Understanding of game elements specifically through abstraction of concepts with specific time limits to ensure that they could be finished within the time allotted and is not too complex to overwhelm learners cognitive load. Dale's Cone of Experience was also followed throughout the design process. Implementation went better than expected applying Anderson's model of online learning except for the technical barriers that should have been realized beforehand. My limitations as a presenter also resurfaced as I continue to tackle public speaking. Overall, evaluation was positive which may also be a cause for bias as I was an honorable member of the

organization. However, I am aware of my own and the workshops shortcomings and applied appropriate solutions for the following sessions.

Since UPOU is an open university and all of our classes are held online, I had difficulty recalling actual theories and principles throughout the different courses and recalled course names instead when I had to connect the decisions to their reasons in the capstone project because of the alternative type of learning. The assessments we went through were different from the traditional type of learning where most of the time we had to apply what we learned which made me focus on what it really means instead of what they are called. Aside from that, Learning Management Systems (LMS) such as the online portal closes after the semester ends and sometimes, I would not be able to download all the readings and even though I may have downloaded all the study guides some links would not be functional. Some courses do have all of the readings and guides provided that I was able to download which was extremely helpful. It is therefore recommended for all the study guides and readings to be available for download for all students before the semester ends or better yet, from the start so that they would have all the materials needed for review even after the LMS closes. Some courses also required us to create ejournals to be posted online on a different personal website of which I used WordPress which also helped since some of the information that I need are already summarized and contextualized in a way that I need without having to go through all of the readings all over again.

Another significant insight was how 4 years into this course and I still haven't properly grasped the difference between an Instructional Designer and a Teacher. I believe that I have focused more on the teaching aspect throughout the development of

the workshop and failed to focus on the intricacies of being a designer. This capstone project was able to point the differences in between as I go beyond the content and instruction and focus on the design instead.

Recommendations

If I was to do it all over again, there are a few things that I wished I was able to execute properly:

Practiced presenting the workshop more effectively, ensuring student engagement and participation by asking them to speak up and share experiences vocally

I would have included the multimedia material in the evaluation form from the pilot testing so as to use it as a field-test. Therefore, I would have some feedback regarding the material and how to improve it for the next iterations.

Timed the whole gameplay from start to finish with the appropriate number of players, chose multiplayer games that could be played simultaneously, or chose single player games with a definite time limit

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Appendices

APPENDIX A

EDS 199 - LOGS

EDS 199
Special Project
Logs

This log is for the students in the Bachelor of Education Studies (BES) program at the University of the Philippines Open University. The student should complete the log after each session, to be validated by the project gatekeeper/ external adviser, depending on the chosen project. The last column is for the project's gatekeeper on the student's work. When the project is finished, a scanned copy of this log sheet shall be submitted as part of the special project portfolio.

Student's name: <u>Jose Alberto Rafael M. Medina</u>
Student number: <u>2013-49431</u> Batch of entry in UPOU: <u>2T SY 2019-2020</u>
Email address: <u>jmedinal@up.edu.ph</u> Contact number: <u>09477477078</u>
Academic Term: 1st term <u>X</u> 2nd term AY: <u>2022-2023</u> 3rd term
Project Locale: <u>University of the Philippines Industrial Engineering Students Organization</u>
Student's Project Main Task: <u>Enhance the yearly seminar held by the organization from planning to execution</u>

Project Week	Specific Date	Specific Time	Duration	Validated by	Highlights	Insights	Gatekeeper's Feedback
Week 1	April 14, 2024	10:30 - 11:00 PM	30 mins	Kyla Salvacion Properties and Holdings Vice President/ Moderator	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Proposal of the chosen topic - Brainstormed for needs, context, and student analysis - Creation of Instructional Plan V1 and V2 	Doing the needs analysis right is solving half the problem by properly defining the gaps	Approved topic chosen, there is no existing financial literacy program for IESO at the moment
Week 2	June 20, 2024	9:20 - 10:00 PM	40 mins	Kyla Salvacion Properties and Holdings Vice President/ Moderator	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Presentation of the Instructional Plan V3 and instructional materials for the workshop - Presentation of Instructor Plan 	Financial literacy can be boring due to the high technicality of the topic, it is up to the instructor on how to make it lively and engaging	Games included as ice breaker are interesting
Week 3	August 11, 2024	8:00 - 9:05 PM	1 hour	Kyla Salvacion Properties and Holdings Vice President/ Moderator	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Workshop proper for module 1 - Presentation of letter of appreciation 	Online classes still suffer from the typical connection problems	Workshop is a success! will propose the actual application for the members within the school year

APPENDIX B

Instructor Guide

Financial Literacy

Budgeting, taxes, loans, savings, investments

General Objective: At the end of the 3-session workshop, students should be able to effectively differentiate assets from liabilities from their own personal balance sheets, to know about the different investment and loan options available in the market and offered by the government, and lastly, to know about the mandatory deductions required by the government.

Specific objectives: At the end of the lesson, students should be able to:

1. Differentiate assets from liabilities
2. Create their own balance sheets
3. Know how to divide their income/allowance
4. Track their expenses

I.Savings and budgeting

Ice-breaker activity (15 mins)

Play cashflow at www.richdad.com (good explanation starting at p.96)

"luck is what happens when preparation meets opportunity - seneca"
Play SPENT at <https://playspent.org/html/> instead due to the long play time

Actual Discussion (30 mins)

Financial Statements 101: Assets, Liabilities, Cash Flow, and Expense Tracking

- Balance sheet - a financial statement that contains details of a company's assets or liabilities at a specific point in time.
- Assets vs liabilities - Assets are the items your company owns that can provide future economic benefit. Liabilities are what you owe other parties.
 - Assets - make money for you.
 - Liabilities - take money from you.
- Loans - difference of simple and compounded interest, time value of money, examples of good and bad loans
- Cash flow - the movement of money in and out of a company.

1. Savings - setting aside a portion of your monthly income

2. Budgeting - a plan on how your money would be spent
3. Financial Literacy - The ability to manage your finances wisely i.e taking out loans, saving for retirement, or get a mortgage

Dividing income to at least 4 portions:

- Expense - For monthly expenses (Food, transportation, utilities)
- Wants- For unnecessary expenses (Vacation, accessories, clothing)
- Emergency - For emergency situations (Friends or family needs help, unplanned necessity)
- Retirement - Saving for the future
- For religious persons, a 5th portion could be allotted to tithes - 10%

Where do you keep your money?

- Banks - traditional physical banks with ATM services i.e BPI, BDO, UB
- Electronic wallets - Applications that allow for electronic transactions i.e Gcash or Maya
- Cash - Physical form of currency such as bank notes or coins

Importance of an Expense tracker - track your expenses and where your money is being applied, better foresight for budgeting

Assessment (10 mins)

Actual division of income based on current expenses

- Budget plan for the month

Wrap-up (5 mins)

Specific objectives: At the end of the lesson, students should be able to:

1. list down different investment options available in the market
2. list down different investment options offered by the government
3. know the different ways investments earn money

II. Investments

Ice breaker activity (20 mins)

Play STAX at <https://buildyourstax.com/>

Actual Discussion (30 mins)

- What is inflation? - rate of increase in prices over a given period of time
- Importance of investing - yearly inflation rate table vs interest rates
- Stocks, forex, crypto – owning a portion of the company

earn in 2 ways dividends and capital appreciation

- dividends - a portion of the company profits that is given to the shareholders

either cash or stock dividends

- capital appreciation - an increase in an investment's market price
- there are two types of people in the market - investor vs trader

Investors take advantage of Money cost averaging, HODL meme

- Money cost averaging - buying a fixed amount at a fixed interval, regardless of the current market condition

Traders study the market and do it as a living, high risk, gamble

- Bonds - A fixed income investment where you put in money for a set period of time usually offered by a company or the government
- Investment/Mutual Funds - Professionally managed investment products
- Treasuries - low to no risk as it is offered by the government, low yield
- Insurance - funds that usually come with health insurance for emergency situations

Assessment (10 mins) - trial account for stock brokers like etoro or col

Wrap up (5 mins)

Specific objectives: At the end of the lesson, students should be able to:

1. Understand Inflation and Investment Returns
2. Distinguishing Investment Types
3. Identify Investment Strategies
4. Evaluate the Concept of Risks and Returns

III. Contributions and taxes

Ice breaker activity (10 mins)

Play Shady Sam at <https://shadysam.com/>

Actual Discussion (30 mins)

SSS Benefits

-Sickness - cash allowance given daily for days unable to work due to injury or sickness

- Maternity - cash allowance given daily for days unable to work due to childbirth, miscarriage, or emergency termination of pregnancy

- Disability - cash benefit as pension for members completely or partially disabled permanently

-Unemployment - one time cash benefit for members involuntarily separated from work

- Retirement - monthly pension or lump sum for inability to work due to old age (60 years old and above)
- Death - monthly pension or lump sum to beneficiaries of a deceased member
- Funeral - cash benefit given for funeral expenses of a deceased member

Pagibig - pag-IBIG (Pagtutulungan sa Kinabukasan: Ikaw, Bangko, Industriya, at Gobyerno) Fund. It is also known as the Home Development Mutual Fund (HDMF).

- a government initiated savings program

Saving programs

Pag-IBIG Fund Regular Savings - reaches maturity after 20 years or withdrawn earlier due to retirement, permanent disability, or critical illness

- as of February 2024, P200 per month by the employee and employer
- earns dividends every year depending on the yearly rate

Modified Pag-IBIG 2 (MP2) Savings

- voluntary savings
- matures in 5 years
- earns a higher dividend rating
- may open several MP2 accounts simultaneously

Housing loans

Pag-IBIG Fund Housing Loan

- for those who want to buy properties (lot, residential house, townhouse, or condominium unit)
- no more than 65 yrs old at the date of application or 70 upon maturity
- may be used for house construction or improvement
- Up to 6 million pesos depending on repricing period, current contributions, and capacity to pay

Home Equity Appreciation Loan (HEAL)

- For members with existing housing loans
- may be used for home improvement, education, health, travel, or capital
- In the US commonly known as Home Equity Line of Credit (HELOC loans)

Pag-IBIG Fund's Affordable Housing Program (AHP) for Minimum-Wage Earners

- A much affordable version of the regular housing loan program for minimum or low income earners

Pag-IBIG Fund Home Saver Programs

- For those unable to make their regular monthly payments
- deferral, repayment plan

Types of taxes

Income tax

- is a tax on a person's income, emoluments, profits arising from property, practice of profession, conduct of trade or on the pertinent items of gross income (BIR)

Value-added Tax (VAT)

- 12% added tax on goods and services

Assessment (10 mins)

Computation of theoretical monthly contributions based on expected income using charts or online calculators

Wrap up (5 mins)

APPENDIX C

Financial Literacy Survey Results (For Students)

Are you a currently a student or an alumni?
10 responses

Do you currently have savings?
5 responses

Age
5 responses

Are you aware of the different investment options?
5 responses

How much is your weekly allowance?
5 responses

Do you currently have an investment among the different options?
5 responses

Are you aware of the required monthly deduction to your salary upon working?
5 responses

Do you want to learn about the different investment options, salary deductions, and government offered loans before graduating college?
5 responses

Are you aware regarding the ranges of the required monthly deduction to your salary upon working?
5 responses

Are you aware of the different loan options offered by these agencies?
5 responses

APPENDIX D

Financial Literacy Survey Results (For Alumni)

Do you currently have savings?
5 responses

At what age can you say did you become aware of the different investment options?
5 responses

Where do you keep your savings?
5 responses

Are you aware regarding the ranges of the required monthly deduction to your salary?
5 responses

Are you aware of the different investment options?
5 responses

Are you aware of the different loan options offered by these agencies?
5 responses

Do you currently have an investment among the different options?
5 responses

At what age can you say did you become aware of the different monthly deductions and loan options?
5 responses

APPENDIX E

. Detailed Lesson Plan

Financial Literacy

Budgeting, taxes, loans, savings, investments

I. Savings and budgeting

Financial Statements 101: Assets, Liabilities, Cash Flow, and Expense Tracking

- Balance sheet - a financial statement that contains details of a company's assets or liabilities at a specific point in time.
- Cash flow - the movement of money in and out of a company.
- Assets vs liabilities - Assets are the items your company owns that can provide future economic benefit. Liabilities are what you owe other parties.
- Assets - make money for you.
- Liabilities - take money from you.
- Loans - difference of simple and compounded interest, time value of money, examples
 - Savings - setting aside a portion of your monthly income
 - Budgeting - a plan on how your money would be spent
 - Financial Literacy - The ability to manage your finances wisely i.e taking out loans, saving for retirement, or get a mortgage

Dividing income to at least 4 portions:

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- Emergency - For emergency situations (Friends or family needs help, unplanned necessity)
- Retirement - Saving for the future
- For religious persons, a 5th portion could be allotted to tithes - 10%

Where do you keep your money?

- Banks - traditional physical banks with ATM and mobile banking services i.e BPI, BDO, UB
- Electronic wallets - Applications that allow for electronic transactions i.e GCash or Maya
- Cash - Physical form of currency such as bank notes or coins

- Maternity - cash allowance given daily for days unable to work due to childbirth, miscarriage, or emergency termination of pregnancy
- Disability - cash benefit as pension for members completely or partially disabled permanently
- Unemployment - one time cash benefit for members involuntarily separated from work
- Retirement - monthly pension or lump sum for inability to work due to old age (60 years old and above)
- Death - monthly pension or lump sum to beneficiaries of a deceased member
- Funeral - cash benefit given for funeral expenses of a deceased member

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- a government initiated savings program

Saving programs

- Pag-IBIG Fund Regular Savings** - reaches maturity after 20 years or withdrawn earlier due to retirement, permanent disability, or critical illness
 - as of February 2024, P200 per month by the employee and employer
 - earns dividends every year depending on the yearly rate

Modified Pag-IBIG 2 (MP2) Savings

- voluntary savings
- matures in 5 years
- earns a higher dividend rate
- may open several MP2 accounts simultaneously

Housing loans

- Pag-IBIG Fund Housing Loan**
 - for those who want to buy properties (lot, residential house, townhouse, or condominium unit)
 - no more than 65 yrs old at the date of application or 70 upon maturity
 - may be used for house construction or improvement

Importance of an Expense tracker - track your expenses and where your money is being applied, better foresight for budgeting

II. Investments

- What is inflation? - rate of increase in prices over a given period of time
- Importance of investing - yearly inflation rate table vs interest rates
- Stocks, forex, crypto - owning a portion of the company earn in 2 ways dividends and capital appreciation (are you gonna say this verbally po?)
- dividends - a portion of the company profits that is given to the shareholders
- either cash or stock dividends (this one too?)
- capital appreciation - an increase in an investment's market price
- there are two types of people in the market - investor vs trader

Investors take advantage of Money cost averaging, HODL meme (2)

- Money cost averaging - buying a fixed amount at a fixed interval, regardless of the current market condition
- Traders study the market and do it as a living, high risk, gamble (3)
- Bonds - A fixed income investment where you put in money for a set period of time usually offered by a company or the government
- Investment/Mutual Funds - Professionally managed investment products
- Treasuries - low to no risk as it is offered by the government, low yield
- Insurance - funds that usually come with health insurance for emergency situations

III. Contributions and taxes

Social Security System (SSS) - The government instituted SSS to provide financial assistance and support to its members (or their dependents) in times of sickness, disability, maternity, old age, calamities, unemployment, or death. For example, financial assistance may come in the form of a salary loan, pension, or

cash allowance. Furthermore, an SSS membership is a lifetime membership and paid contributions are non-withdrawable.
SSS Contribution - 14% - 9.5% by the employer and 4.5% by the employee

Range of Contribution	Minimum Monthly Salary	Maximum Monthly Salary	Minimum Monthly Contribution	Maximum Monthly Contribution
0 - P1,000	P1,000	P1,000	P140	P140
P1,001 - P2,000	P2,000	P2,000	P280	P280
P2,001 - P3,000	P3,000	P3,000	P420	P420
P3,001 - P4,000	P4,000	P4,000	P560	P560
P4,001 - P5,000	P5,000	P5,000	P700	P700
P5,001 - P6,000	P6,000	P6,000	P840	P840
P6,001 - P7,000	P7,000	P7,000	P980	P980
P7,001 - P8,000	P8,000	P8,000	P1,120	P1,120
P8,001 - P9,000	P9,000	P9,000	P1,260	P1,260
P9,001 - P10,000	P10,000	P10,000	P1,400	P1,400
P10,001 - P11,000	P11,000	P11,000	P1,540	P1,540
P11,001 - P12,000	P12,000	P12,000	P1,680	P1,680
P12,001 - P13,000	P13,000	P13,000	P1,820	P1,820
P13,001 - P14,000	P14,000	P14,000	P1,960	P1,960
P14,001 - P15,000	P15,000	P15,000	P2,100	P2,100
P15,001 - P16,000	P16,000	P16,000	P2,240	P2,240
P16,001 - P17,000	P17,000	P17,000	P2,380	P2,380
P17,001 - P18,000	P18,000	P18,000	P2,520	P2,520
P18,001 - P19,000	P19,000	P19,000	P2,660	P2,660
P19,001 - P20,000	P20,000	P20,000	P2,800	P2,800
P20,001 - P21,000	P21,000	P21,000	P2,940	P2,940
P21,001 - P22,000	P22,000	P22,000	P3,080	P3,080
P22,001 - P23,000	P23,000	P23,000	P3,220	P3,220
P23,001 - P24,000	P24,000	P24,000	P3,360	P3,360
P24,001 - P25,000	P25,000	P25,000	P3,500	P3,500
P25,001 - P26,000	P26,000	P26,000	P3,640	P3,640
P26,001 - P27,000	P27,000	P27,000	P3,780	P3,780
P27,001 - P28,000	P28,000	P28,000	P3,920	P3,920
P28,001 - P29,000	P29,000	P29,000	P4,060	P4,060
P29,001 - P30,000	P30,000	P30,000	P4,200	P4,200
P30,001 - P31,000	P31,000	P31,000	P4,340	P4,340
P31,001 - P32,000	P32,000	P32,000	P4,480	P4,480
P32,001 - P33,000	P33,000	P33,000	P4,620	P4,620
P33,001 - P34,000	P34,000	P34,000	P4,760	P4,760
P34,001 - P35,000	P35,000	P35,000	P4,900	P4,900
P35,001 - P36,000	P36,000	P36,000	P5,040	P5,040
P36,001 - P37,000	P37,000	P37,000	P5,180	P5,180
P37,001 - P38,000	P38,000	P38,000	P5,320	P5,320
P38,001 - P39,000	P39,000	P39,000	P5,460	P5,460
P39,001 - P40,000	P40,000	P40,000	P5,600	P5,600
P40,001 - P41,000	P41,000	P41,000	P5,740	P5,740
P41,001 - P42,000	P42,000	P42,000	P5,880	P5,880
P42,001 - P43,000	P43,000	P43,000	P6,020	P6,020
P43,001 - P44,000	P44,000	P44,000	P6,160	P6,160
P44,001 - P45,000	P45,000	P45,000	P6,300	P6,300
P45,001 - P46,000	P46,000	P46,000	P6,440	P6,440
P46,001 - P47,000	P47,000	P47,000	P6,580	P6,580
P47,001 - P48,000	P48,000	P48,000	P6,720	P6,720
P48,001 - P49,000	P49,000	P49,000	P6,860	P6,860
P49,001 - P50,000	P50,000	P50,000	P7,000	P7,000

Monthly SSS Contribution Table 2023 to 2024: Minimum and Maximum Monthly Salary

SSS Benefits

- Sickness - cash allowance given daily for days unable to work due to injury or sickness

- Up to 6 million pesos depending on repricing period, current contributions, and capacity to pay

Rates per Repricing Period, effective 01 July 2024

Repricing Period	Rate
1-yr Fixing	5.750%
3-yr Fixing	5.250%
5-yr Fixing	6.500%
10-yr Fixing	7.125%
15-yr Fixing	7.750%
20-yr Fixing	8.500%
25-yr Fixing	8.125%
30-yr Fixing	9.750%

Home Equity Appreciation Loan (HEAL)

- For members with existing housing loans
- may be used for home improvement, education, health, travel, or capital
- In the US commonly known as Home Equity Line of Credit (HELOC loans)

Pag-IBIG Fund's Affordable Housing Program (AHP) for Minimum-Wage Earners

- A much affordable version of the regular housing loan program for minimum or low income earners

Pag-IBIG Fund Home Saver Programs

- For those unable to make their regular monthly payments
- deferral, repayment plan

Types of taxes

Income tax

- is a tax on a person's income, emoluments, profits arising from property, practice of profession, conduct of trade or the pertinent items of gross income (BIR)

Income	Rate
0 - PHP 250,000	0
PHP 250,001 - PHP 400,000	15
PHP 400,001 - PHP 800,000	20
PHP 800,001 - PHP 2,000,000	25
PHP 2,000,001 - PHP 8,000,000	30
Above 8,000,000	35

Value-added Tax (VAT)

- 12% added tax on goods and services

References:

- Goff, K. (2023, December 28). *What are assets, liabilities and equity?*. Bankrate. <https://www.bankrate.com/loans/small-business/assets-liabilities-equity/#:~:text=Assets%20are%20things%20that%20add,issue%20your%20company%20a%20loan.>
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- Nikki. (2024, July 24). *Pag-ibig contribution schedule [2022 guide]*: Eezi. Eezi HR Technologies Corp. <https://www.eezi.com/pag-ibig-contribution-schedule/>

APPENDIX F

Financial Literacy PPT Version 1

Presented by Jose Alberto Rafael M. Medina

Understanding Financial Literacy: Markets, Trade, and Finance Essentials

A Guide to Personal Finance: Budgeting, Taxes, Loans, Savings, and Investments

LEARNING ACTIVITY:
Play cashflow at www.richdad.com

Savings and Budgeting

Rich Dad Poor Dad
WHAT THE RICH TEACH THEIR KIDS ABOUT MONEY - THAT THE POOR AND MIDDLE CLASS DO NOT!

ROBERT T. KIYOSAKI

Financial Statements 101: Assets, Liabilities, Cash Flow, and Expense Tracking

- **BALANCE SHEET** - a financial statement that contains details of a company's assets or liabilities at a specific point in time.
- **CASH FLOW** - the movement of money in and out of a company.
- **LOANS** - difference of simple and compounded interest, time value of money

Savings and Budgeting

Assets VS Liabilities

Assets are the items your company owns that can provide future economic benefit. Liabilities are what you owe other parties.

ASSETS - make money for you.

LIABILITIES - take money from you.

Savings and Budgeting

Savings Setting aside a portion of your monthly income.

Budgeting A plan on how your money would be spent

Financial Literacy The ability to manage your finances wisely i.e taking out loans, saving for retirement, or get a mortgage

Savings and Budgeting

Dividing Income to at Least 4 Portions:

- **Expense** - For monthly expenses (food, transportation, utilities)
- **Wants** - For unnecessary expenses (vacation, accessories, clothing)
- **Emergency** - For emergency situations (friends or family needs help, unplanned necessity)
- **Retirement** - Saving for the future
- For religious persons, a 5th portion could be allotted to tithes - 10%

Savings and Budgeting

Banks

Traditional physical banks with ATM and mobile banking services i.e BPI, BDO, UB

Electronic Wallets

Applications that allow for electronic transactions i.e Gcash or Maya

Cash

Physical form of currency such as bank notes or coins

Savings and Budgeting

Where do you keep your money?

Savings and Budgeting

IMPORTANCE OF AN EXPENSE TRACKER

track your expenses and where your money is being applied, better foresight for budgeting

Savings and Budgeting

Assessment: Create your own personal cashflow and balance sheet

Savings and Budgeting

"luck is what happens when preparation meets opportunity"

-Seneca

Savings and Budgeting

02.

Investments

What is inflation?

The rate of increase in prices over a given period of time

Importance of Investing

Yearly inflation rate table vs interest rates

Stocks, Forex, Crypto

Owning a portion of the company

Investments

Dividends

A portion of the company profits that is given to the shareholders

Capital Appreciation

An increase in an investment's market price

Investments

Investors

Traders

Investments

Money Cost Averaging

Buying a fixed amount at a fixed interval, regardless of the current market condition

Treasuries

Low to no risk as it is offered by the government (low yield)

A fixed income investment where you put in money for a set period of time usually offered by a company or the government

Bonds

A fixed income investment where you put in money for a set period of time usually offered by a company or the government

Insurance

Investment/Mutual Funds

Professionally managed investment products

Investments

Investments

Assessment: trial account for stock brokers like etoro or col

(yeah no i still dunno what the assessments r 4)

Investments

Social Security System (SSS)

The government instituted SSS to provide financial assistance and support to its members (or their dependents) in times of sickness, disability, maternity, old age, calamities, unemployment, or death. For example, financial assistance may come in the form of a salary loan, pension, or cash allowance. Furthermore, an SSS membership is a lifetime membership and paid contributions are non-withdrawable.

SSS Contribution - 14% - 9.5% by the employer and 4.5% by the employee

Contributions and Taxes

Range of Compensation		MINIMUM SALARY CREDIT		Regular Contributions	
Min.	Max.	Regular Contribution	Employer Share	Employee Share	
17,000.00	17,100.00	17,050.00	4,000.00	2,925.00	690.00
17,100.00	17,200.00	17,150.00	4,000.00	2,925.00	690.00
17,200.00	17,300.00	17,250.00	4,000.00	2,925.00	690.00
17,300.00	17,400.00	17,350.00	4,000.00	2,925.00	690.00
17,400.00	17,500.00	17,450.00	4,000.00	2,925.00	690.00
17,500.00	17,600.00	17,550.00	4,000.00	2,925.00	690.00
17,600.00	17,700.00	17,650.00	4,000.00	2,925.00	690.00
17,700.00	17,800.00	17,750.00	4,000.00	2,925.00	690.00
17,800.00	17,900.00	17,850.00	4,000.00	2,925.00	690.00
17,900.00	18,000.00	17,950.00	4,000.00	2,925.00	690.00
18,000.00	18,100.00	18,050.00	4,000.00	2,925.00	690.00
18,100.00	18,200.00	18,150.00	4,000.00	2,925.00	690.00
18,200.00	18,300.00	18,250.00	4,000.00	2,925.00	690.00
18,300.00	18,400.00	18,350.00	4,000.00	2,925.00	690.00
18,400.00	18,500.00	18,450.00	4,000.00	2,925.00	690.00
18,500.00	18,600.00	18,550.00	4,000.00	2,925.00	690.00
18,600.00	18,700.00	18,650.00	4,000.00	2,925.00	690.00
18,700.00	18,800.00	18,750.00	4,000.00	2,925.00	690.00
18,800.00	18,900.00	18,850.00	4,000.00	2,925.00	690.00
18,900.00	19,000.00	18,950.00	4,000.00	2,925.00	690.00
19,000.00	19,100.00	19,050.00	4,000.00	2,925.00	690.00
19,100.00	19,200.00	19,150.00	4,000.00	2,925.00	690.00
19,200.00	19,300.00	19,250.00	4,000.00	2,925.00	690.00
19,300.00	19,400.00	19,350.00	4,000.00	2,925.00	690.00
19,400.00	19,500.00	19,450.00	4,000.00	2,925.00	690.00
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19,600.00	19,700.00	19,650.00	4,000.00	2,925.00	690.00
19,700.00	19,800.00	19,750.00	4,000.00	2,925.00	690.00
19,800.00	19,900.00	19,850.00	4,000.00	2,925.00	690.00
19,900.00	20,000.00	19,950.00	4,000.00	2,925.00	690.00
20,000.00	20,100.00	20,050.00	4,000.00	2,925.00	690.00
20,100.00	20,200.00	20,150.00	4,000.00	2,925.00	690.00
20,200.00	20,300.00	20,250.00	4,000.00	2,925.00	690.00
20,300.00	20,400.00	20,350.00	4,000.00	2,925.00	690.00
20,400.00	20,500.00	20,450.00	4,000.00	2,925.00	690.00
20,500.00	20,600.00	20,550.00	4,000.00	2,925.00	690.00
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20,700.00	20,800.00	20,750.00	4,000.00	2,925.00	690.00
20,800.00	20,900.00	20,850.00	4,000.00	2,925.00	690.00
20,900.00	21,000.00	20,950.00	4,000.00	2,925.00	690.00
21,000.00	21,100.00	21,050.00	4,000.00	2,925.00	690.00
21,100.00	21,200.00	21,150.00	4,000.00	2,925.00	690.00
21,200.00	21,300.00	21,250.00	4,000.00	2,925.00	690.00
21,300.00	21,400.00	21,350.00	4,000.00	2,925.00	690.00
21,400.00	21,500.00	21,450.00	4,000.00	2,925.00	690.00
21,500.00	21,600.00	21,550.00	4,000.00	2,925.00	690.00
21,600.00	21,700.00	21,650.00	4,000.00	2,925.00	690.00
21,700.00	21,800.00	21,750.00	4,000.00	2,925.00	690.00
21,800.00	21,900.00	21,850.00	4,000.00	2,925.00	690.00
21,900.00	22,000.00	21,950.00	4,000.00	2,925.00	690.00
22,000.00	22,100.00	22,050.00	4,000.00	2,925.00	690.00
22,100.00	22,200.00	22,150.00	4,000.00	2,925.00	690.00
22,200.00	22,300.00	22,250.00	4,000.00	2,925.00	690.00
22,300.00	22,400.00	22,350.00	4,000.00	2,925.00	690.00
22,400.00	22,500.00	22,450.00	4,000.00	2,925.00	690.00
22,500.00	22,600.00	22,550.00	4,000.00	2,925.00	690.00
22,600.00	22,700.00	22,650.00	4,000.00	2,925.00	690.00
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22,800.00	22,900.00	22,850.00	4,000.00	2,925.00	690.00
22,900.00	23,000.00	22,950.00	4,000.00	2,925.00	690.00
23,000.00	23,100.00	23,050.00	4,000.00	2,925.00	690.00
23,100.00	23,200.00	23,150.00	4,000.00	2,925.00	690.00
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23,400.00	23,500.00	23,450.00	4,000.00	2,925.00	690.00
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23,900.00	24,000.00	23,950.00	4,000.00	2,925.00	690.00
24,000.00	24,100.00	24,050.00	4,000.00	2,925.00	690.00
24,100.00	24,200.00	24,150.00	4,000.00	2,925.00	690.00
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24,900.00	25,000.00	24,950.00	4,000.00	2,925.00	690.00
25,000.00	25,100.00	25,050.00	4,000.00	2,925.00	690.00
25,100.00	25,200.00	25,150.00	4,000.00	2,925.00	690.00
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26,100.00	26,200.00	26,150.00	4,000.00	2,925.00	690.00
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27,100.00	27,200.00	27,150.00	4,000.00	2,925.00	690.00
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28,300.00	28,400.00	28,350.00	4,000.00	2,925.00	690.00
28,400.00	28,500.00	28,450.00	4,000.00	2,925.00	690.00
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28,600.00	28,700.00	28,650.00	4,000.00	2,925.00	690.00
28,700.00	28,800.00	28,750.00	4,000.00	2,925.00	690.00
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29,100.00	29,200.00	29,150.00	4,000.00	2,925.00	690.00
29,200.00	29,300.00	29,250.00	4,000.00	2,925.00	690.00
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29,900.00	30,000.00	29,950.00	4,000.00	2,925.00	690.00
30,000.00	30,100.00	30,050.00	4,000.00	2,925.00	690.00
30,100.00	30,200.00	30,150.00	4,000.00	2,925.00	690.00
30,200.00	30,300.00	30,250.00	4,000.00	2,925.00	690.00
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30,600.00	30,700.00	30,650.00	4,000.00	2,925.00	690.00
30,700.00	30,800.00	30,750.00	4,000.00	2,925.00	690.00
30,800.00	30,900.00	30,850.00	4,000.00	2,925.00	690.00
30,900.00	31,000.00	30,950.00	4,000.00	2,925.00	690.00
31,000.00					

PAG-IBIG

Pag-IBIG (Pagtutulongan sa Kinabukasan: Ikaw, Bangko, Industriya, at Gobyerno) Fund.

- It is also known as the Home Development Mutual Fund (HDMF).
- A government initiated savings program

Contributions and Taxes

SAVING PROGRAMS

Contributions and Taxes

PAG-IBIG FUND REGULAR SAVINGS

- Reaches maturity after 20 years or withdrawn earlier due to retirement, permanent disability, or critical illness
- As of February 2024, P200 per month by the employee and employer
- Earns dividends every year depending on the yearly rate

Contributions and Taxes

MODIFIED PAG-IBIG 2 (MP2) SAVINGS

- voluntary savings
- matures in 5 years
- earns a higher dividend rating
- may open several MP2 accounts simultaneously

Contributions and Taxes

Housing Loans

Contributions and Taxes

Pag-IBIG Fund Housing Loan

- for those who want to buy properties (lot, residential house, townhouse, or condominium unit)
- no more than 65 yrs old at the date of application or 70 upon maturity
- may be used for house construction or improvement
- Up to 6 million pesos depending on repricing period, current contributions, and capacity to pay

Contributions and Taxes

RATES PER REPRICING PERIOD, EFFECTIVE 01 JULY 2024	
1-Yr Fixing	5.750%
3-Yr Fixing	6.250%
5-Yr Fixing	6.500%
10-Yr Fixing	7.125%
15-Yr Fixing	7.750%
20-Yr Fixing	8.500%
25-Yr Fixing	9.125%
30-Yr Fixing	9.750%

Contributions and Taxes

HOME EQUITY APPRECIATION LOAN (HEAL)

- For members with existing housing loans
- May be used for home improvement, education, health, travel, or capital
- In the US commonly known as Home Equity Line of Credit (HELOC loans)

Contributions and Taxes

PAG-IBIG FUND'S AFFORDABLE HOUSING PROGRAM (AHP) FOR MINIMUM-WAGE EARNERS

- A much affordable version of the regular housing loan program for minimum or low income earners

Contributions and Taxes

PAG-IBIG FUND HOME SAVER PROGRAMS

- For those unable to make their regular monthly payments
- Deferral, repayment plan

Contributions and Taxes

TYPES OF TAXES

Income tax

is a tax on a person's income, emoluments, profits arising from property, practice of profession, conduct of trade or on the pertinent items of gross income (BIR)

Personal Income Tax Rates in the Philippines	
Income	2024 tax rate (%)
0 - PHP 250,000 (US\$4,279)	0
PHP 250,001 (US\$4,279) - PHP 400,000 (US\$6,848)	15
PHP 400,001 (US\$6,848) - PHP 800,000 (US\$13,697)	20
PHP 800,001 (US\$13,697) - PHP 2,000,000 (US\$34,242)	25
PHP 2,000,001 (US\$34,242) - PHP 8,000,000 (US\$136,972)	30
Above 8,000,000 (US\$136,972)	35

TYPES OF TAXES

Value-added Tax (VAT)

a consumption tax on goods and services levied at each stage of the supply chain where value is added.

12% added tax
on goods and
services

Assessment (10 mins)

Computation of theoretical monthly contributions based on expected income using charts or online calculators

Savings and Budgeting

REFERENCE:

- Goff, K. (2023, December 28). What are assets, liabilities and equity?. Bankrate. <https://www.bankrate.com/loans/small-business/assets-liabilities-equity/>
- Hayes, A. (n.d.). Cash flow: What it is, how it works, and how to analyze it. Investopedia. <https://www.investopedia.com/terms/c/cashflow.asp#~:text=Cash%20flow%20is%20the%20movement,use%20of%20cash%20var%20times>
- Nibali, (2024, July 24). Pag-ibig contribution schedule (2022 guide). Ecol. Ecol HR Technologies Corp. <https://www.ecol.com/pag-ibig-contribution-schedule/>
- Toom, T. I. (n.d.). What is value-added tax (VAT)? Investopedia. <https://www.investopedia.com/terms/v/valueaddedtax.asp#~:text=The%20term%20value%20added%20tax,to%20the%20point%20of%20sale>

APPENDIX G

Lesson Plan with Assessments

Financial Literacy

Budgeting, taxes, loans, savings, investments

I. Savings and budgeting

Learning Activity: Play SPENT at https://playspent.org/

Financial Statements 101: Assets, Liabilities, Cash Flow, and Expense Tracking

- Balance sheet - a financial statement that contains details of a company's assets or liabilities at a specific point in time.
• Cash flow - the movement of money in and out of a company.
• Assets vs liabilities - Assets are the items your company owns that can provide future economic benefit. Liabilities are what you owe other parties.
• Assets - make money for you.
• Liabilities - take money from you.
• Loans - difference of simple and compounded interest, time value of money, examples

1. Savings - setting aside a portion of your monthly income
2. Budgeting - a plan on how your money would be spent
3. Financial Literacy - The ability to manage your finances wisely i.e taking out loans, saving for retirement, or get a mortgage

Dividing income to at least 4 portions:

- Expense - For monthly expenses (Food, transportation, utilities)
• Wants- For unnecessary expenses (Vacation, accessories, clothing)
• Emergency - For emergency situations (Friends or family needs help, unplanned necessity)
• Retirement - Saving for the future
• For religious persons, a 5th portion could be allotted to tithes - 10%

Where do you keep your money?

Table with 4 columns: Range of Contributions, SSS, Pag-IBIG, and Regular Contributions. It lists various contribution ranges and their corresponding SSS and Pag-IBIG values.

Monthly SSS Contribution Table 2023 to 2024: Minimum and Maximum Monthly Salary

SSS Benefits

- Sickness - cash allowance given daily for days unable to work due to injury or sickness
-Maternity - cash allowance given daily for days unable to work due to childbirth, miscarriage, or emergency termination of pregnancy
-Disability - cash benefit as pension for members completely or partially disabled permanently
-Unemployment - one time cash benefit for members involuntarily separated from work
-Retirement - monthly pension or lump sum for inability to work due to old age (60 years old and above)
-Death - monthly pension or lump sum to beneficiaries of a deceased member
-Funeral - cash benefit given for funeral expenses of a deceased member

Pagbigig - pag-IBIG (Pagtutulungan sa Kinabukasan: Ikaw, Bangko, Industriya, at Gobyerno) Fund. It is also known as the Home Development Mutual Fund (HDMF). - a government initiated savings program

- Banks - traditional physical banks with ATM and mobile banking services i.e BPI, BDO, UB
• Electronic wallets - Applications that allow for electronic transactions i.e Gcash or Maya
• Cash - Physical form of currency such as bank notes or coins

Importance of an Expense tracker - track your expenses and where your money is being applied, better foresight for budgeting

Assessment: Balance sheet for the month - Actual division of income (allowance) based on current expenses

II. Investments

Learning activity: play STAX at https://buildyourstax.com/

- What is inflation? - rate of increase in prices over a given period of time
• Importance of investing - yearly inflation rate table vs Interest rates
• Stocks, forex, crypto - owning a portion of the company earn in 2 ways dividends and capital appreciation (are you gonna say this verbally po?)
• dividends - a portion of the company profits that is given to the shareholders

either cash or stock dividends (this one too!)
• capital appreciation - an increase in an investment's market price
• there are two types of people in the market - investor vs trader

Investors take advantage of Money cost averaging, HODL meme (2)

- Money cost averaging - buying a fixed amount at a fixed interval, regardless of the current market condition
Traders study the market and do it as a living, high risk, gamble (3)
• Bonds - A fixed income investment where you put in money for a set period of time usually offered by a company or the government

- Investment/Mutual Funds - Professionally managed investment products
• Treasuries - low to no risk as it is offered by the government, low yield
• Insurance - funds that usually come with health insurance for emergency situations

Assessment: trial account for stock brokers like etoro or col

III. Contributions and taxes

Learning activity: play SHADY SAM at https://shadysam.com/

the government instituted SSS to provide financial assistance and support to its members (or their dependents) in times of sickness, disability, maternity, old age, calamities, unemployment, or death. For example, financial assistance may come in the form of a salary loan, pension, or cash allowance. Furthermore, an SSS membership is a lifetime membership and paid contributions are non-withdrawable.

SSS Contribution - 14% - 9.5% by the employer and 4.5% by the employee

Table with 4 columns: Range of Contributions, SSS, Pag-IBIG, and Regular Contributions. It lists various contribution ranges and their corresponding SSS and Pag-IBIG values.

Table with 2 columns: Saving programs and Rates. 25-Yr Fixing: 9.125%, 30-Yr Fixing: 9.750%

Home Equity Appreciation Loan (HEAL)

- For members with existing housing loans
- may be used for home improvement, education, health, travel, or capital
- In the US commonly known as Home Equity Line of Credit (HELOC loans)

Pag-IBIG Fund's Affordable Housing Program (AHP) for Minimum-Wage Earners

- A much affordable version of the regular housing loan program for minimum or low income earners

Pag-IBIG Fund Home Saver Programs

- For those unable to make their regular monthly payments - deferral, repayment plan

Types of taxes

Income tax

- is a tax on a person's income, emoluments, profits arising from property, practice of profession, conduct of trade or on the pertinent items of gross income (BIR)

Table titled 'Personal Income Tax Rates in the Philippines' showing Income ranges and 2024 tax rate (%). Example: 0 - PHP 250,000: 0; PHP 250,001 - PHP 400,000: 15

Saving programs

Pag-IBIG Fund Regular Savings - reaches maturity after 20 years or withdrawn earlier due to retirement, permanent disability, or critical illness

- as of February 2024, P200 per month by the employee and employer
- earns dividends every year depending on the yearly rate

Modified Pag-IBIG 2 (MP2) Savings

- voluntary savings
- matures in 5 years
- earns a higher dividend rating
- may open several MP2 accounts simultaneously

Housing loans

Pag-IBIG Fund Housing Loan

- for those who want to buy properties (lot, residential house, townhouse, or condominium unit)
- no more than 65 yrs old at the date of application or 70 upon maturity
- may be used for house construction or improvement
- Up to 6 million pesos depending on repricing period, current contributions, and capacity to pay

Table titled 'Rates per Repricing Period, effective 01 July 2024' showing repricing periods and rates: 1-Yr Fixing: 5.750%, 3-Yr Fixing: 6.250%, 5-Yr Fixing: 6.500%, 10-Yr Fixing: 7.125%, 15-Yr Fixing: 7.750%, 20-Yr Fixing: 8.500%

PHP 400,001 – PHP 800,000	20
PHP 800,001 – PHP 2,000,000	25
PHP 2,000,001 – PHP 8,000,000	30
Above 8,000,000	35

Value-added Tax (VAT)

- 12% added tax on goods and services

Assessment: Computation of theoretical monthly contributions based on expected income using charts or online calculators

References:

- Goff, K. (2023, December 28). *What are assets, liabilities and equity?*. Bankrate. <https://www.bankrate.com/loans/small-business/assets-liabilities-equity/#:~:text=Assets%20are%20things%20that%20add,issue%20y,our%20company%20a%20loan.>
- Hayes, A. (n.d.). *Cash flow: What it is, how it works, and how to analyze it*. Investopedia. <https://www.investopedia.com/terms/c/cashflow.asp#:~:text=Cash%20flow%20is%20the%20movement,use%20of%20cash%20over%20time.>
- Nikki. (2024, July 24). *Pag-ibig contribution schedule [2022 guide]: Eezi*. Eezi HR Technologies Corp. <https://www.eezi.com/pag-ibig-contribution-schedule/>

APPENDIX H

STAX companion sheet

**NGPF Activity Bank
Investing**
[Teacher Tip Video](#)

INTERACTIVE: Invest with STAX!

Interactive: [NGPF's STAX](#)

Do YOU have what it takes to be an expert investor? See if you can beat the market in a 20-year period and then answer the reflection questions down below. Good luck!

Cheat Sheet:

- Review the [STAX: Portfolio Dashboard Reference](#) to familiarize yourself with how the game looks.
- There are 7 different types of investment opportunities that will be explained in the information boxes. For extra help during the game, click the question mark at the top right of the asset box.
- Every 6 months (30 seconds in the game), you receive **pocket cash** to invest.
 - **Pocket cash** represents 10% of your salary that you are saving.
 - Your **pocket cash** starts at \$2,000 and increases over time as you get raises and bonuses!
- Click on the double arrows button to toggle between **balance** and **profit** for each investment opportunity.
- When you are finished with the game, keep your STAX results window open to answer the questions below.

Reflection Questions:

1. Take a screenshot of your portfolio at the end of the game and paste it in the box below.

2. What approximate percentage did you have in each asset class? Complete the table below using the Investment Portfolio pie chart. Estimate the percentage for each of the asset classes using the pie chart as a reference.

Type of Asset	Savings Account	Certificate of Deposit	Index Fund	Individual Stocks	Government bonds	Commodity Crops	Gold
Dollar Amount							
Percentage							

3. Looking at the table above, did you finish the game with a diversified portfolio? Explain.

4. Describe your investment strategy as you played the game.
- What was your plan when you first started playing and how did it change during the course of the game?
 - If you didn't have a strategy, why not?

5. Describe the various emotions you felt as you played the game. How did your emotions impact your decision-making while playing the game? Provide specific examples.

6. What strategy did the computer follow? Why do you think that strategy was so successful in beating so many of the students in your class?

7. Your friend brags, "It was easy to try to beat the computer in the STAX game. I made \$100,000 more with my strategy of actively trading those individual stocks. Why would you want to just buy an index fund? It's so much fun to try to beat the market!" How would you respond?

8. If you had the opportunity to play STAX a second time, what would be your strategy?

9. What do you think would be the consequences of having less money saved for retirement? How would that impact your life?

10. **Bonus Question:** You had seven different investment options in the game. The most diversified portfolio would include all of these various options. On average, should this diversified portfolio have the highest return? Why or why not?

Appendix I

Financial Literacy PPT Final Version

Presented by Jose Alberto Rafael M. Medina

Understanding Financial Literacy: Markets, Trade, and Finance Essentials

A Guide to Personal Finance: Budgeting, Taxes, Loans, Savings, and Investments

LEARNING ACTIVITY:
Play SPENT at www.richdad.com

Urban Ministries of Durham serves over 6,000 people every year. But you'd never need help, right?

PROVE IT
ACCEPT THE CHALLENGE

SPENT

Savings and Budgeting

Financial Statements 101: Assets, Liabilities, Cash Flow, and Expense Tracking

- **BALANCE SHEET** - a financial statement that contains details of a company's assets or liabilities at a specific point in time.
- **CASH FLOW** - the movement of money in and out of a company.
- **LOANS** - difference of simple and compounded interest, time value of money

Savings and Budgeting

Assets VS Liabilities

Assets are the items your company owns that can provide future economic benefit. Liabilities are what you owe other parties.

ASSETS - make money for you.

LIABILITIES - take money from you.

Savings and Budgeting

Savings Setting aside a portion of your monthly income.

Budgeting A plan on how your money would be spent

Financial Literacy The ability to manage your finances wisely i.e taking out loans, saving for retirement, or get a mortgage

Savings and Budgeting

Dividing Income to at Least 4 Portions:

- **Expense** - For monthly expenses (food, transportation, utilities)
- **Wants** - For unnecessary expenses (vacation, accessories, clothing)
- **Emergency** - For emergency situations (friends or family needs help, unplanned necessity)
- **Retirement** - Saving for the future
- For religious persons, a 5th portion could be allotted to tithes - 10%

Savings and Budgeting

Banks

Traditional physical banks with ATM and mobile banking services i.e BPI, BDO, UB

Electronic Wallets

Applications that allow for electronic transactions i.e Gcash or Maya

Cash

Physical form of currency such as bank notes or coins

Savings and Budgeting

Where do you keep your money?

Savings and Budgeting

IMPORTANCE OF AN EXPENSE TRACKER

track your expenses and where your money is being applied, better foresight for budgeting

Savings and Budgeting

Assessment: Create your own personal cashflow and balance sheet

Savings and Budgeting

"luck is what happens when preparation meets opportunity"

-Seneca

Savings and Budgeting

02.

Investments

What is inflation?

The rate of increase in prices over a given period of time

Importance of Investing

Yearly inflation rate table vs interest rates

Stocks, Forex, Crypto

Owning a portion of the company

LEARNING ACTIVITY:

Play STAX at

<https://buildyourstax.com/>

Investment

Dividends

A portion of the company profits that is given to the shareholders

Capital Appreciation

An increase in an investment's market price

Investments

Investors

Traders

Investments

Money Cost Averaging

Buying a fixed amount at a fixed interval, regardless of the current market condition

A fixed income investment where you put in money for a set period of time usually offered by a company or the government

Bonds

Investment/Mutual Funds

Professionally managed investment products

Investments

Treasuries Low to no risk as it is offered by the government (low yield)

A fixed income investment where you put in money for a set period of time usually offered by a company or the government

Insurance

Assessment: trial account for stock brokers like etoro or col

(yeah no i still dunno what the assessments r 4)

Investments

Investments

03.

Contributions and Taxes

LEARNING ACTIVITY:
Play SHADY SAM at
<https://shadysam.com/>

Investment

Social Security System (SSS)

The government instituted SSS to provide financial assistance and support to its members (or their dependents) in times of sickness, disability, maternity, old age, calamities, unemployment, or death. For example, financial assistance may come in the form of a salary loan, pension, or cash allowance. Furthermore, an SSS membership is a lifetime membership and paid contributions are non-withdrawable.

SSS Contribution - 14% - 9.5% by the employer and 4.5% by the employee

Range of Compensation		MONTHLY SALARY SHARE		Regular Cash Benefits	
Min.	Max.	Employer Contribution	Employee Share	Employer Share	Employee Share
0.00	4,200.00	6,000.00	600.00	600.00	600.00
4,200.00	4,700.00	6,600.00	660.00	660.00	660.00
4,700.00	5,200.00	7,200.00	720.00	720.00	720.00
5,200.00	5,700.00	7,800.00	780.00	780.00	780.00
5,700.00	6,200.00	8,400.00	840.00	840.00	840.00
6,200.00	6,700.00	9,000.00	900.00	900.00	900.00
6,700.00	7,200.00	9,600.00	960.00	960.00	960.00
7,200.00	7,700.00	10,200.00	1,020.00	1,020.00	1,020.00
7,700.00	8,200.00	10,800.00	1,080.00	1,080.00	1,080.00
8,200.00	8,700.00	11,400.00	1,140.00	1,140.00	1,140.00
8,700.00	9,200.00	12,000.00	1,200.00	1,200.00	1,200.00
9,200.00	9,700.00	12,600.00	1,260.00	1,260.00	1,260.00
9,700.00	10,200.00	13,200.00	1,320.00	1,320.00	1,320.00
10,200.00	10,700.00	13,800.00	1,380.00	1,380.00	1,380.00
10,700.00	11,200.00	14,400.00	1,440.00	1,440.00	1,440.00
11,200.00	11,700.00	15,000.00	1,500.00	1,500.00	1,500.00
11,700.00	12,200.00	15,600.00	1,560.00	1,560.00	1,560.00
12,200.00	12,700.00	16,200.00	1,620.00	1,620.00	1,620.00
12,700.00	13,200.00	16,800.00	1,680.00	1,680.00	1,680.00
13,200.00	13,700.00	17,400.00	1,740.00	1,740.00	1,740.00
13,700.00	14,200.00	18,000.00	1,800.00	1,800.00	1,800.00
14,200.00	14,700.00	18,600.00	1,860.00	1,860.00	1,860.00
14,700.00	15,200.00	19,200.00	1,920.00	1,920.00	1,920.00
15,200.00	15,700.00	19,800.00	1,980.00	1,980.00	1,980.00
15,700.00	16,200.00	20,400.00	2,040.00	2,040.00	2,040.00
16,200.00	16,700.00	21,000.00	2,100.00	2,100.00	2,100.00
16,700.00	17,200.00	21,600.00	2,160.00	2,160.00	2,160.00
17,200.00	17,700.00	22,200.00	2,220.00	2,220.00	2,220.00
17,700.00	18,200.00	22,800.00	2,280.00	2,280.00	2,280.00
18,200.00	18,700.00	23,400.00	2,340.00	2,340.00	2,340.00
18,700.00	19,200.00	24,000.00	2,400.00	2,400.00	2,400.00
19,200.00	19,700.00	24,600.00	2,460.00	2,460.00	2,460.00
19,700.00	20,200.00	25,200.00	2,520.00	2,520.00	2,520.00

Monthly SSS Contribution Table 2023 to 2024 Minimum and Maximum Monthly Salary (table check thoroughly for visual purposes only)

Contributions and Taxes

Contributions and Taxes

Treasuries Low to no risk as it is offered by the government (low yield)

A fixed income investment where you put in money for a set period of time usually offered by a company or the government
Insurance

Assessment: trial account for stock brokers like etoro or col

(yeah no i still dunno what the assessments r 4)

Investments

Investments

03.

Contributions and Taxes

LEARNING ACTIVITY:
 Play SHADY SAM at
<https://shadysam.com/>

Investment

Social Security System (SSS)

The government instituted SSS to provide financial assistance and support to its members (or their dependents) in times of sickness, disability, maternity, old age, calamities, unemployment, or death. For example, financial assistance may come in the form of a salary loan, pension, or cash allowance.

Furthermore, an SSS membership is a lifetime membership and paid contributions are non-withdrawable.

SSS Contribution - 14% - 9.5% by the employer and 4.5% by the employee

Contributions and Taxes

Range of Compensation		MINIMUM SALARY (MSE 100.00)		Regular Cash Benefits	
Min.	Max.	Employer Contribution	Employee Share	Unemployment	Maternity
0.00	4,250.00	6,375.00	301.00	421.00	421.00
4,250.00	4,750.00	6,937.50	324.00	452.00	452.00
4,750.00	5,250.00	7,500.00	347.00	483.00	483.00
5,250.00	5,750.00	8,062.50	370.00	514.00	514.00
5,750.00	6,250.00	8,625.00	393.00	545.00	545.00
6,250.00	6,750.00	9,187.50	416.00	576.00	576.00
6,750.00	7,250.00	9,750.00	439.00	607.00	607.00
7,250.00	7,750.00	10,312.50	462.00	638.00	638.00
7,750.00	8,250.00	10,875.00	485.00	669.00	669.00
8,250.00	8,750.00	11,437.50	508.00	700.00	700.00
8,750.00	9,250.00	12,000.00	531.00	731.00	731.00
9,250.00	9,750.00	12,562.50	554.00	762.00	762.00
9,750.00	10,250.00	13,125.00	577.00	793.00	793.00
10,250.00	10,750.00	13,687.50	600.00	824.00	824.00
10,750.00	11,250.00	14,250.00	623.00	855.00	855.00
11,250.00	11,750.00	14,812.50	646.00	886.00	886.00
11,750.00	12,250.00	15,375.00	669.00	917.00	917.00
12,250.00	12,750.00	15,937.50	692.00	948.00	948.00
12,750.00	13,250.00	16,500.00	715.00	979.00	979.00
13,250.00	13,750.00	17,062.50	738.00	1,010.00	1,010.00
13,750.00	14,250.00	17,625.00	761.00	1,041.00	1,041.00
14,250.00	14,750.00	18,187.50	784.00	1,072.00	1,072.00
14,750.00	15,250.00	18,750.00	807.00	1,103.00	1,103.00
15,250.00	15,750.00	19,312.50	830.00	1,134.00	1,134.00
15,750.00	16,250.00	19,875.00	853.00	1,165.00	1,165.00
16,250.00	16,750.00	20,437.50	876.00	1,196.00	1,196.00
16,750.00	17,250.00	21,000.00	899.00	1,227.00	1,227.00
17,250.00	17,750.00	21,562.50	922.00	1,258.00	1,258.00
17,750.00	18,250.00	22,125.00	945.00	1,289.00	1,289.00
18,250.00	18,750.00	22,687.50	968.00	1,320.00	1,320.00
18,750.00	19,250.00	23,250.00	991.00	1,351.00	1,351.00
19,250.00	19,750.00	23,812.50	1,014.00	1,382.00	1,382.00
19,750.00	20,250.00	24,375.00	1,037.00	1,413.00	1,413.00
20,250.00	20,750.00	24,937.50	1,060.00	1,444.00	1,444.00
20,750.00	21,250.00	25,500.00	1,083.00	1,475.00	1,475.00
21,250.00	21,750.00	26,062.50	1,106.00	1,506.00	1,506.00
21,750.00	22,250.00	26,625.00	1,129.00	1,537.00	1,537.00
22,250.00	22,750.00	27,187.50	1,152.00	1,568.00	1,568.00
22,750.00	23,250.00	27,750.00	1,175.00	1,599.00	1,599.00
23,250.00	23,750.00	28,312.50	1,198.00	1,630.00	1,630.00
23,750.00	24,250.00	28,875.00	1,221.00	1,661.00	1,661.00
24,250.00	24,750.00	29,437.50	1,244.00	1,692.00	1,692.00
24,750.00	25,250.00	30,000.00	1,267.00	1,723.00	1,723.00
25,250.00	25,750.00	30,562.50	1,290.00	1,754.00	1,754.00
25,750.00	26,250.00	31,125.00	1,313.00	1,785.00	1,785.00
26,250.00	26,750.00	31,687.50	1,336.00	1,816.00	1,816.00
26,750.00	27,250.00	32,250.00	1,359.00	1,847.00	1,847.00
27,250.00	27,750.00	32,812.50	1,382.00	1,878.00	1,878.00
27,750.00	28,250.00	33,375.00	1,405.00	1,909.00	1,909.00
28,250.00	28,750.00	33,937.50	1,428.00	1,940.00	1,940.00
28,750.00	29,250.00	34,500.00	1,451.00	1,971.00	1,971.00
29,250.00	29,750.00	35,062.50	1,474.00	2,002.00	2,002.00
29,750.00	30,250.00	35,625.00	1,497.00	2,033.00	2,033.00
30,250.00	30,750.00	36,187.50	1,520.00	2,064.00	2,064.00
30,750.00	31,250.00	36,750.00	1,543.00	2,095.00	2,095.00
31,250.00	31,750.00	37,312.50	1,566.00	2,126.00	2,126.00
31,750.00	32,250.00	37,875.00	1,589.00	2,157.00	2,157.00
32,250.00	32,750.00	38,437.50	1,612.00	2,188.00	2,188.00
32,750.00	33,250.00	39,000.00	1,635.00	2,219.00	2,219.00
33,250.00	33,750.00	39,562.50	1,658.00	2,250.00	2,250.00
33,750.00	34,250.00	40,125.00	1,681.00	2,281.00	2,281.00
34,250.00	34,750.00	40,687.50	1,704.00	2,312.00	2,312.00
34,750.00	35,250.00	41,250.00	1,727.00	2,343.00	2,343.00
35,250.00	35,750.00	41,812.50	1,750.00	2,374.00	2,374.00
35,750.00	36,250.00	42,375.00	1,773.00	2,405.00	2,405.00
36,250.00	36,750.00	42,937.50	1,796.00	2,436.00	2,436.00
36,750.00	37,250.00	43,500.00	1,819.00	2,467.00	2,467.00
37,250.00	37,750.00	44,062.50	1,842.00	2,498.00	2,498.00
37,750.00	38,250.00	44,625.00	1,865.00	2,529.00	2,529.00
38,250.00	38,750.00	45,187.50	1,888.00	2,560.00	2,560.00
38,750.00	39,250.00	45,750.00	1,911.00	2,591.00	2,591.00
39,250.00	39,750.00	46,312.50	1,934.00	2,622.00	2,622.00
39,750.00	40,250.00	46,875.00	1,957.00	2,653.00	2,653.00
40,250.00	40,750.00	47,437.50	1,980.00	2,684.00	2,684.00
40,750.00	41,250.00	48,000.00	2,003.00	2,715.00	2,715.00
41,250.00	41,750.00	48,562.50	2,026.00	2,746.00	2,746.00
41,750.00	42,250.00	49,125.00	2,049.00	2,777.00	2,777.00
42,250.00	42,750.00	49,687.50	2,072.00	2,808.00	2,808.00
42,750.00	43,250.00	50,250.00	2,095.00	2,839.00	2,839.00
43,250.00	43,750.00	50,812.50	2,118.00	2,870.00	2,870.00
43,750.00	44,250.00	51,375.00	2,141.00	2,901.00	2,901.00
44,250.00	44,750.00	51,937.50	2,164.00	2,932.00	2,932.00
44,750.00	45,250.00	52,500.00	2,187.00	2,963.00	2,963.00
45,250.00	45,750.00	53,062.50	2,210.00	2,994.00	2,994.00
45,750.00	46,250.00	53,625.00	2,233.00	3,025.00	3,025.00
46,250.00	46,750.00	54,187.50	2,256.00	3,056.00	3,056.00
46,750.00	47,250.00	54,750.00	2,279.00	3,087.00	3,087.00
47,250.00	47,750.00	55,312.50	2,302.00	3,118.00	3,118.00
47,750.00	48,250.00	55,875.00	2,325.00	3,149.00	3,149.00
48,250.00	48,750.00	56,437.50	2,348.00	3,180.00	3,180.00
48,750.00	49,250.00	57,000.00	2,371.00	3,211.00	3,211.00
49,250.00	49,750.00	57,562.50	2,394.00	3,242.00	3,242.00
49,750.00	50,250.00	58,125.00	2,417.00	3,273.00	3,273.00
50,250.00	50,750.00	58,687.50	2,440.00	3,304.00	3,304.00
50,750.00	51,250.00	59,250.00	2,463.00	3,335.00	3,335.00
51,250.00	51,750.00	59,812.50	2,486.00	3,366.00	3,366.00
51,750.00	52,250.00	60,375.00	2,509.00	3,397.00	3,397.00
52,250.00	52,750.00	60,937.50	2,532.00	3,428.00	3,428.00
52,750.00	53,250.00	61,500.00	2,555.00	3,459.00	3,459.00
53,250.00	53,750.00	62,062.50	2,578.00	3,490.00	3,490.00
53,750.00	54,250.00	62,625.00	2,601.00	3,521.00	3,521.00
54,250.00	54,750.00	63,187.50	2,624.00	3,552.00	3,552.00
54,750.00	55,250.00	63,750.00	2,647.00	3,583.00	3,583.00
55,250.00	55,750.00	64,312.50	2,670.00	3,614.00	3,614.00
55,750.00	56,250.00	64,875.00	2,693.00	3,645.00	3,645.00
56,250.00	56,750.00	65,437.50	2,716.00	3,676.00	3,676.00
56,750.00	57,250.00	66,000.00	2,739.00	3,707.00	3,707.00
57,250.00	57,750.00	66,562.50	2,762.00	3,738.00	3,738.00
57,750.00	58,250.00	67,125.00	2,785.00	3,769.00	3,769.00
58,250.00	58,750.00	67,687.50	2,808.00	3,800.00	3,800.00
58,750.00	59,250.00	68,250.00	2,831.00	3,831.00	3,831.00
59,250.00	59,750.00	68,812.50	2,854.00	3,862.00	3,862.00
59,750.00	60,250.00	69,375.00	2,877.00	3,893.00	3,893.00
60,250.00	60,750.00	69,937.50	2,900.00	3,924.00	3,924.00
60,750.00	61,250.00	70,500.00	2,923.00	3,955.00	3,955.00
61,250.00	61,750.00	71,062.50	2,946.00	3,986.00	3,986.00
61,750.00	62,250.00	71,625.00	2,969.00	4,017.00	4,017.00
62,250.00	62,750.00	72,187.50	2,992.00	4,048.00	4,048.00
62,750.00	63,250.00	72,750.00	3,015.00	4,079.00	4,079.00
63,250.00	63,750.00	73,312.50	3,038.00	4,110.00	4,110.00
63,750.00	64,250.00	73,875.00	3,061.00	4,141.00	4,141.00
64,250.00	64,750.00	74,437.50	3,084.00	4,172.00	4,172.00
64,750.00	65,250.00	75,000.00	3,107.00	4,203.00	4,203.00
65,250.00	65,750.00	75,562.50	3,130.00	4,234.00	4,234.00
65,750.00	66,250.00	76,125.00	3,153.00	4,265.00	4,265.00
66,250.00	66,750.00	76,687.50	3,176.00	4,296.00	4,296.00
66,750.00	67,250.00	77,250.00	3,199.00	4,327.00	4,327.00
67,250.00	67,750.00	77,812.50	3,222.00	4,358.00	4,358.00
67,750.00	68,250.00	78,375.00	3,245.00	4,389.00	4,389.00
68,250.00	68,750.00	78,937.50	3,268.00	4,420.00	4,420.00
68,750.00	69,250.00	79,500.00	3,291.00	4,451.00	4,451.00
69,250.00	69,750.00	80,062.50	3,314.00	4,482.00	4,482.00
69,750.00	70,250.00	80,625.00	3,337.00	4,513.00	4,513.00

Treasuries Low to no risk as it is offered by the government (low yield)

A fixed income investment where you put in money for a set period of time usually offered by a company or the government
Insurance

Assessment: trial account for stock brokers like etoro or col

(yeah no i still dunno what the assessments r 4)

Investments

Investments

03.
Contributions and Taxes

LEARNING ACTIVITY:
Play SHADY SAM at
<https://shadysam.com/>

Investment

Social Security System (SSS)

The government instituted SSS to provide financial assistance and support to its members (or their dependents) in times of sickness, disability, maternity, old age, calamities, unemployment, or death. For example, financial assistance may come in the form of a salary loan, pension, or cash allowance. Furthermore, an SSS membership is a lifetime membership and paid contributions are non-withdrawable.

SSS Contribution - 14% - 9.5% by the employer and 4.5% by the employee

Contributions and Taxes

Range of Compensation		MONTHLY SALARY SHARE		Regular Cash Benefits	
Min.	Max.	Employer Contribution	Employee Share	Employee Share	Employee Share
0.00	4,200.00	0.00	160.00	300.00	300.00
4,200.00	4,700.00	0.00	160.00	400.00	400.00
4,700.00	5,200.00	0.00	160.00	475.00	475.00
5,200.00	5,700.00	0.00	160.00	550.00	550.00
5,700.00	6,200.00	0.00	160.00	625.00	625.00
6,200.00	6,700.00	0.00	160.00	700.00	700.00
6,700.00	7,200.00	0.00	160.00	775.00	775.00
7,200.00	7,700.00	0.00	160.00	850.00	850.00
7,700.00	8,200.00	0.00	160.00	925.00	925.00
8,200.00	8,700.00	0.00	160.00	1,000.00	1,000.00
8,700.00	9,200.00	0.00	160.00	1,075.00	1,075.00
9,200.00	9,700.00	0.00	160.00	1,150.00	1,150.00
9,700.00	10,200.00	0.00	160.00	1,225.00	1,225.00
10,200.00	10,700.00	0.00	160.00	1,300.00	1,300.00
10,700.00	11,200.00	0.00	160.00	1,375.00	1,375.00
11,200.00	11,700.00	0.00	160.00	1,450.00	1,450.00
11,700.00	12,200.00	0.00	160.00	1,525.00	1,525.00
12,200.00	12,700.00	0.00	160.00	1,600.00	1,600.00
12,700.00	13,200.00	0.00	160.00	1,675.00	1,675.00
13,200.00	13,700.00	0.00	160.00	1,750.00	1,750.00
13,700.00	14,200.00	0.00	160.00	1,825.00	1,825.00
14,200.00	14,700.00	0.00	160.00	1,900.00	1,900.00
14,700.00	15,200.00	0.00	160.00	1,975.00	1,975.00
15,200.00	15,700.00	0.00	160.00	2,050.00	2,050.00
15,700.00	16,200.00	0.00	160.00	2,125.00	2,125.00
16,200.00	16,700.00	0.00	160.00	2,200.00	2,200.00
16,700.00	17,200.00	0.00	160.00	2,275.00	2,275.00
17,200.00	17,700.00	0.00	160.00	2,350.00	2,350.00
17,700.00	18,200.00	0.00	160.00	2,425.00	2,425.00
18,200.00	18,700.00	0.00	160.00	2,500.00	2,500.00
18,700.00	19,200.00	0.00	160.00	2,575.00	2,575.00
19,200.00	19,700.00	0.00	160.00	2,650.00	2,650.00
19,700.00	20,200.00	0.00	160.00	2,725.00	2,725.00
20,200.00	20,700.00	0.00	160.00	2,800.00	2,800.00
20,700.00	21,200.00	0.00	160.00	2,875.00	2,875.00
21,200.00	21,700.00	0.00	160.00	2,950.00	2,950.00
21,700.00	22,200.00	0.00	160.00	3,025.00	3,025.00
22,200.00	22,700.00	0.00	160.00	3,100.00	3,100.00
22,700.00	23,200.00	0.00	160.00	3,175.00	3,175.00
23,200.00	23,700.00	0.00	160.00	3,250.00	3,250.00
23,700.00	24,200.00	0.00	160.00	3,325.00	3,325.00
24,200.00	24,700.00	0.00	160.00	3,400.00	3,400.00
24,700.00	25,200.00	0.00	160.00	3,475.00	3,475.00
25,200.00	25,700.00	0.00	160.00	3,550.00	3,550.00
25,700.00	26,200.00	0.00	160.00	3,625.00	3,625.00
26,200.00	26,700.00	0.00	160.00	3,700.00	3,700.00
26,700.00	27,200.00	0.00	160.00	3,775.00	3,775.00
27,200.00	27,700.00	0.00	160.00	3,850.00	3,850.00
27,700.00	28,200.00	0.00	160.00	3,925.00	3,925.00
28,200.00	28,700.00	0.00	160.00	4,000.00	4,000.00
28,700.00	29,200.00	0.00	160.00	4,075.00	4,075.00
29,200.00	29,700.00	0.00	160.00	4,150.00	4,150.00
29,700.00	30,200.00	0.00	160.00	4,225.00	4,225.00
30,200.00	30,700.00	0.00	160.00	4,300.00	4,300.00
30,700.00	31,200.00	0.00	160.00	4,375.00	4,375.00
31,200.00	31,700.00	0.00	160.00	4,450.00	4,450.00
31,700.00	32,200.00	0.00	160.00	4,525.00	4,525.00
32,200.00	32,700.00	0.00	160.00	4,600.00	4,600.00
32,700.00	33,200.00	0.00	160.00	4,675.00	4,675.00
33,200.00	33,700.00	0.00	160.00	4,750.00	4,750.00
33,700.00	34,200.00	0.00	160.00	4,825.00	4,825.00
34,200.00	34,700.00	0.00	160.00	4,900.00	4,900.00
34,700.00	35,200.00	0.00	160.00	4,975.00	4,975.00
35,200.00	35,700.00	0.00	160.00	5,050.00	5,050.00
35,700.00	36,200.00	0.00	160.00	5,125.00	5,125.00
36,200.00	36,700.00	0.00	160.00	5,200.00	5,200.00
36,700.00	37,200.00	0.00	160.00	5,275.00	5,275.00
37,200.00	37,700.00	0.00	160.00	5,350.00	5,350.00
37,700.00	38,200.00	0.00	160.00	5,425.00	5,425.00
38,200.00	38,700.00	0.00	160.00	5,500.00	5,500.00
38,700.00	39,200.00	0.00	160.00	5,575.00	5,575.00
39,200.00	39,700.00	0.00	160.00	5,650.00	5,650.00
39,700.00	40,200.00	0.00	160.00	5,725.00	5,725.00
40,200.00	40,700.00	0.00	160.00	5,800.00	5,800.00
40,700.00	41,200.00	0.00	160.00	5,875.00	5,875.00
41,200.00	41,700.00	0.00	160.00	5,950.00	5,950.00
41,700.00	42,200.00	0.00	160.00	6,025.00	6,025.00
42,200.00	42,700.00	0.00	160.00	6,100.00	6,100.00
42,700.00	43,200.00	0.00	160.00	6,175.00	6,175.00
43,200.00	43,700.00	0.00	160.00	6,250.00	6,250.00
43,700.00	44,200.00	0.00	160.00	6,325.00	6,325.00
44,200.00	44,700.00	0.00	160.00	6,400.00	6,400.00
44,700.00	45,200.00	0.00	160.00	6,475.00	6,475.00
45,200.00	45,700.00	0.00	160.00	6,550.00	6,550.00
45,700.00	46,200.00	0.00	160.00	6,625.00	6,625.00
46,200.00	46,700.00	0.00	160.00	6,700.00	6,700.00
46,700.00	47,200.00	0.00	160.00	6,775.00	6,775.00
47,200.00	47,700.00	0.00	160.00	6,850.00	6,850.00
47,700.00	48,200.00	0.00	160.00	6,925.00	6,925.00
48,200.00	48,700.00	0.00	160.00	7,000.00	7,000.00
48,700.00	49,200.00	0.00	160.00	7,075.00	7,075.00
49,200.00	49,700.00	0.00	160.00	7,150.00	7,150.00
49,700.00	50,200.00	0.00	160.00	7,225.00	7,225.00
50,200.00	50,700.00	0.00	160.00	7,300.00	7,300.00
50,700.00	51,200.00	0.00	160.00	7,375.00	7,375.00
51,200.00	51,700.00	0.00	160.00	7,450.00	7,450.00
51,700.00	52,200.00	0.00	160.00	7,525.00	7,525.00
52,200.00	52,700.00	0.00	160.00	7,600.00	7,600.00
52,700.00	53,200.00	0.00	160.00	7,675.00	7,675.00
53,200.00	53,700.00	0.00	160.00	7,750.00	7,750.00
53,700.00	54,200.00	0.00	160.00	7,825.00	7,825.00
54,200.00	54,700.00	0.00	160.00	7,900.00	7,900.00
54,700.00	55,200.00	0.00	160.00	7,975.00	7,975.00
55,200.00	55,700.00	0.00	160.00	8,050.00	8,050.00
55,700.00	56,200.00	0.00	160.00	8,125.00	8,125.00
56,200.00	56,700.00	0.00	160.00	8,200.00	8,200.00
56,700.00	57,200.00	0.00	160.00	8,275.00	8,275.00
57,200.00	57,700.00	0.00	160.00	8,350.00	8,350.00
57,700.00	58,200.00	0.00	160.00	8,425.00	8,425.00
58,200.00	58,700.00	0.00	160.00	8,500.00	8,500.00
58,700.00	59,200.00	0.00	160.00	8,575.00	8,575.00
59,200.00	59,700.00	0.00	160.00	8,650.00	8,650.00
59,700.00	60,200.00	0.00	160.00	8,725.00	8,725.00
60,200.00	60,700.00	0.00	160.00	8,800.00	8,800.00
60,700.00	61,200.00	0.00	160.00	8,875.00	8,875.00
61,200.00	61,700.00	0.00	160.00	8,950.00	8,950.00
61,700.00	62,200.00	0.00	160.00	9,025.00	9,025.00
62,200.00	62,700.00	0.00	160.00	9,100.00	9,100.00
62,700.00	63,200.00	0.00	160.00	9,175.00	9,175.00
63,200.00	63,700.00	0.00	160.00	9,250.00	9,250.00
63,700.00	64,200.00	0.00	160.00	9,325.00	9,325.00
64,200.00	64,700.00	0.00	160.00	9,400.00	9,400.00
64,700.00	65,200.00	0.00	160.00	9,475.00	9,475.00
65,200.00	65,700.00	0.00	160.00	9,550.00	9,550.00
65,700.00	66,200.00	0.00	160.00	9,625.00	9,625.00
66,200.00	66,700.00	0.00	160.00	9,700.00	9,700.00
66,700.00	67,200.00	0.00	160.00	9,775.00	9,775.00
67,200.00	67,700.00	0.00	160.00	9,850.00	9,850.00
67,700.00	68,200.00	0.00	160.00	9,925.00	9,925.00
68,200.00	68,700.00	0.00	160.00	10,000.00	10,000.00

Monthly SSS Contribution Table 2023 to 2024. Minimum and Maximum Monthly Salary (table check the entry for visual purposes only)

Contributions and Taxes

TYPES OF TAXES

Income tax

is a tax on a person's income, emoluments, profits arising from property, practice of profession, conduct of trade or on the pertinent items of gross income (BIR)

Personal Income Tax Rates in the Philippines	
Income	2024 tax rate (%)
0 – PHP 250,000 (US\$4,279)	0
PHP 250,001 (US\$4,279) – PHP 400,000 (US\$6,848)	15
PHP 400,001 (US\$6,848) – PHP 800,000 (US\$13,697)	20
PHP 800,001 (US\$13,697) – PHP 2,000,000 (US\$34,242)	25
PHP 2,000,001 (US\$34,242) – PHP 8,000,000 (US\$136,972)	30
Above 8,000,000 (US\$136,972)	35

Assessment (10 mins)

Computation of theoretical monthly contributions based on expected income using charts or online calculators

Savings and Budgeting

TYPES OF TAXES

Value-added Tax (VAT)

a consumption tax on goods and services levied at each stage of the supply chain where value is added.

12% added tax
on goods and
services

REFERENCE:

- Coft, K. (2023, December 28). What are assets, liabilities and equity? Bankrate. [https://www.bankrate.com/loans/small-business/assets-liabilities-equity/#:text=Assets%20are%20things%20that%20add%20value%20to%20your%20company%20or%20loan,](https://www.bankrate.com/loans/small-business/assets-liabilities-equity/#:text=Assets%20are%20things%20that%20add%20value%20to%20your%20company%20or%20loan,https://www.investopedia.com/terms/c/cash-flow.asp#:text=Cash%20flow%20is%20the%20movement,use%20of%20cash%20over%20time.)
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- Team, T. I. (n.d.). What is value-added tax (VAT)? Investopedia. <https://www.investopedia.com/terms/v/value-added-tax.asp#:text=The%20term%20value%20added%20tax,to%20the%20point%20of%20sale.>

Appendix J

Assessment Results

CASHFLOW & NETWORTH

Income:
Weekly Allowance

Expenses:
Pamasahe
Dorm and utilities rent
Food
Load

Assets:
Laptop

PARTICIPANT 1

Income:
Allowance from tita
SA

Expenses:
Food and groceries
Drinks
Transportation
Gas for cooking
school supplies
Load or Data

PARTICIPANT 2

Income:
Monthly Allowance

Expenses:
Dorm Rent
Utilities Expense
Food Expense
Academic Expenses
Personal Wants

Assets:
Personal Computer

PARTICIPANT 3

Income:
Allowance from parents

Expenses:
Food
Transportation
Groceries
Wants

Liabilities:
Dorm fees

PARTICIPANT 4

Income:
**Allowance from parents/
Scholarship**

Expenses:
Dorm fees
Food cravings
Personal amenities
Extracurricular expenses
Academic supplies
Hygiene
Load

PARTICIPANT 5